

STEM EDUCATION CONFERENCE
DUBLIN, IRELAND | 2026

Book of Abstracts

SMEC 2026 STEM Education Conference

Hosted by DCU's Centre for the Advancement of
STEM Teaching and Learning (CASTeL)

DCU's St Patricks Campus
11th & 12th June 2026

We welcome you to the 11th SMEC STEM Education conference, hosted by DCU's CASTeL (Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning).

Abstracts in this book are presented alphabetically by family name of the corresponding author.

Addressing global challenges requires all STEM Education disciplines to act together, with other disciplines and with our broader communities. We are living through a defining moment for our planet. We face converging crises of climate breakdown and biodiversity loss, alongside the challenges and opportunities presented by technological advancements and AI.

In a world of fast-moving information cycles, STEM literacy in the general population is critical. All of these require STEM skills to be combined with a social focus; STEM Education has never been more important, or more complex.

This year, we explore how STEM Education – in the form of scientific inquiry, mathematical reasoning, engineering design, and technological innovation – can come together to foster a resilient and hopeful future, in partnership with our learners and our communities.

“How do we equip learners with the knowledge to understand and navigate complex systems, the skills to engineer sustainable solutions, and the empathy to protect and steward our environment and community?”

SMEC 2026 Organising Committee

David Whittaker (Chair)

School of STEM Education, Innovation & Global Studies; Institute of Education, Dublin City University.

Dr Aoibhinn Ní Shúilleabháin

School of STEM Education, Innovation & Global Studies; Institute of Education, Dublin City University.

Dr Leah Ridgway

School of Electronic Engineering; Faculty of Engineering & Computing, Dublin City University.

Dr. Paul van Kampen

School of Physical Sciences; Faculty of Science & Health, Dublin City University.

SMEC STEM Education Conference Website: castel.ie/smec-stem-education-conference

Conference Programme: conftool.org/smec2026/sessions.php

Online Book of Abstracts: zenodo.org/records/20344027

SMEC is hosted by the DCU Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching & Learning (CASTeL):

Website: castel.ie

LinkedIn: <https://bit.ly/49p2FwM> (or search: DCU CASTeL)

Wednesday 10th June 2026

<p>6:00pm - 8:30pm</p>	<p>Student Pre-Conference: Student Pre-Conference Kicking off the main SMEC 2026 conference, this evening event is a supportive, open setting for students to present their ideas and receive constructive feedback with a selection of 10 minute presentations followed by 5 minutes Q&A.</p> <p>Attendance at the pre-conference is free for all – students, professional staff, and academics. Please note that registration for this evening event does not include registration for the full SMEC 2026 conference on Thursday and Friday</p> <p>If you are registered for SMEC 2026 we invite you to support our early career colleagues.</p> <p>For numbers and catering purposes, please complete registration here: http://bit.ly/3PFtshz</p> <p>The evening will include light refreshments and networking.</p>
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Thursday 11th June 2026

<p>8:30am - 9:30am</p>	<p>Registration - Day 1</p>			
<p>9:20am - 9:35am</p>	<p>Welcome Address: Conference Opening by DCU President, Prof Daire Keogh Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p>			
<p>9:35am - 10:35am</p>	<p>Keynote 1: Learning Science, the skills that come and those that remain - Prof Wouter van Joolingen Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p>			
<p>10:40am - 11:40am</p>	<p>PS-A Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Design of an inquiry-based learning laboratory on concepts of earth and space <u>Gammell, Stephen</u>^{1,2}; <u>McLoughlin, Eilish</u>^{1,2} 1: Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland; 2: Centre for Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning, Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland.</p> <p>How Irish Primary Teachers Performed on Spatial Ability Tasks and Its Relationship with STEM Classroom Engagement <u>Ó Tuairisg, Cormac Máirtín</u>; <u>Brady, Mark</u>; <u>Pagkratidou, Marianna</u> DCU, Ireland</p> <p>A thematic analysis of teachers' experiences of professional development to teach spatial ability <u>Khuanazarova, Ganiina</u>¹; <u>Duffy, Gavin</u>¹; <u>Sorby, Sheryl</u>² 1: TU Dublin, Ireland; 2: Michigan Technological University</p>	<p>PS-B Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Mapping pre-school early number learning progressions <u>Venkat, Hamsa</u>; <u>Lattimore, Brenda</u>; <u>Gillic, Cora</u>; <u>O'Reilly, Nicola</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p> <p>Young Children's Conceptions of Luck and Its Influence on Their Probabilistic Judgements <u>Kingston, Mary</u>^{1,2} 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: CASTeL</p> <p>Mathematics and language across borders: Exploring pedagogical actions on Irish-language use <u>Ryan, Miriam</u>; <u>Harbison, Lorraine</u>; <u>NíChonghaile, Deirdre</u>; <u>Venkat, Hamsa</u> DCU, Ireland</p>	<p>PS-C Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Co-Designing VR Chemistry Labs for Post-primary Education in Ireland <u>Hamash, Mahmoud</u>¹; <u>Tiernan, Peter</u>¹; <u>William Young, Gareth</u>² 1: School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, Institute of Education, Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: School of Computer Science and Statistics, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland</p> <p>STEM Education in Practice: Designing Authentic and Gender-Responsive Informatics Learning with the THINKER Framework <u>Mangina, Eleni</u>; <u>Gorgu, Levent</u> UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, Ireland</p> <p>Using Virtual Reality to Bridge Disciplinary Knowledge Gaps in Pre-Service Junior Cycle Science Teachers in Ireland <u>Hamash, Mahmoud</u>; <u>O'Neill, Natalie</u>; <u>Tiernan, Peter</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p>	<p>PS-D Location: Room D204 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Exploring Teachers' Use of Number Lines <u>Nic Mhuirí, Siún</u>^{1,2}; <u>Groenewald, Carien</u>³ 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: CASTeL; 3: OLICO Mathematics Education</p> <p>Gender Issues: Assessment Design, Confidence, and Access in High-Stakes Mathematics Education <u>Loftus, Jennifer</u>; <u>O'Leary, Eoghan</u>; <u>Duffy, Meighan</u>; <u>Goodall, Janet</u>; <u>Punzet, Horst</u>; <u>North, Ben</u>; <u>Oldham, Elizabeth</u> Society of Actuaries in Ireland</p>
<p>11:40am - 12:10pm</p>	<p>Posters-1 Location: Room D204 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Bridging the Maths Gap - Initial Design of Maths-Focused Tutorial Worksheets for First-Year Undergraduate Physics Students <u>O'Connor, Gary</u>¹; <u>van Kampen, Paul</u>²; <u>Grimes, Paul</u>¹ 1: Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning and School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, DCU Institute of Education, Dublin City University; 2: Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning and School of Physical Sciences, Dublin City University</p> <p>Electronics for Climate Creativity <u>Ramachandran, Sivakumar</u>; <u>Burke, Claire</u>; <u>Downey, Sam</u> IADT Dun Laoghaire, Ireland</p> <p>Connecting the Dots: Theoretical Perspectives Informing Effective Teaching of Spatial Reasoning in Geometry <u>Love, Chelsea Leigh</u> University College Cork, Ireland</p> <p>Do you want to make a battery? Insights from the development and evaluation of an accessible STEM public engagement activity <u>O'Donoghue, John</u> Trinity College Dublin, Ireland</p>		<p>Posters-2 Location: Room D205 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Spatial Ability and Scientific Reasoning as Predictors of Performance on Motion Graphs Among Junior Cycle Science Students <u>Harding, Rachel</u>; <u>Duffy, Gavin</u> TU Dublin, Ireland</p> <p>Contextualisation in educational research: a case study demonstrating the relationship between a study's motivation, the featured data and the analysis method <u>Howard, Emma</u>; <u>White, Arthur</u>; <u>Wyse, Jason</u> School of Computer Science and Statistics, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland</p> <p>Gesture as a Pedagogical Resource in Undergraduate Mathematics <u>Tyrrell-Nic Dhonncha, Brian</u> Queen's University Belfast, Ireland</p> <p>Developing Educator Noticing of Children's Mathematical Structural Awareness <u>Venkat, Hamsa</u>; <u>Lattimore, Brenda</u>; <u>Cora, Gillic</u>; <u>Nicola, O'Reilly</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p> <p>Beyond Floating and Sinking: Narrative-Led Engineering in the Primary Science Classroom <u>Ó hAnluain, Colm</u> Gaelscoil na Laochra, Ireland</p>	

	<p>Beyond the Algorithm: Reclaiming the Human Element in AI-Enhanced Science Communication <u>Malone, Fiona</u> Atlantic Technological University, Ireland</p> <p>Combating Gender Biases in the use of AI in Secondary Education through Feminist Education Innovations <u>Sáinz Ibáñez, Milagros¹; Schaper, Marie Monique²; Bivol, Miruna¹; Segura, Rocio¹; Romano, María José¹; Lopez, Beatriz¹</u> 1: Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain; 2: University of Lleida</p> <p>The Role of Teacher Noticing in Mathematics Classroom Discourse <u>McMahon, Mary</u> Mary Immaculate College, Ireland</p> <p>Four Seasons One World: A Project from the Towards Inclusion Pilot Program. Abstract <u>Whitlow, Patrick; Callan Gough, Judith</u> NCSE, Ireland</p>	<p>Authentic Datasets in Secondary Science: A Systematic Review of Classroom Integration and Impacts <u>Kelly, Regina; Dundon, Patrick</u> University of Limerick, Ireland</p> <p>Action Video Games as a Form of Spatial Training: Comparing Virtual Reality to Traditional Computers with Relation to Mathematics Ability. <u>O'Flaherty, Conor; Pagkratidou, Marianna</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p> <p>Integrating AI enabled Indicators in Adapting the Rubric for Assessing Project Based Learning with Digital Technologies <u>Charania, Amina¹; Lautre, Vinay²; Leahy, Margaret¹; Singh, Raason²</u> 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India</p> <p>Enhancing STEM/STEAM Accessibility: Educator Awareness and Instructional Responses to Colour Vision Deficiency Through Experiential Learning <u>Smith - Lozada, Ann</u> St. John's University, United States of America</p>		
12:10pm - 1:00pm	<p>Lunch - Day 1 Location: Staffroom/Quad (Outside area)</p>			
1:00pm - 2:00pm	<p>PS-E Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Speaking Mathematics: Oral Assessment in Analysis <u>Neuschel, Thorsten; Ni Fhloinn, Eabhnat</u> DCU, Ireland</p> <p>An investigation into first year undergraduate students' thoughts while engaging with procedural and problem-solving questions in mathematics <u>Matthews, Lauren¹; Faulkner, Fiona²; Robinson, Paul³; Prendergast, Mark⁴</u> 1: Technological University Dublin, Ireland; 2: Technological University Dublin; 3: Technological University Dublin; 4: University College Cork</p> <p>Fostering critical thinking in mathematics through analysing reasoning tasks <u>Breen, Sinead¹; O'Shea, Ann²</u> 1: DCU, Ireland; 2: Maynooth University, Ireland</p>	<p>PS-F Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>The SPARK Project: Cultivating STEM Literacies for Planetary Health and Agency <u>Fitzpatrick, Michelle; O'Dwyer, Anne; Hourigan, Mairéad; Leavy, Aisling; Carroll, Claire; Ryan, Mairéad; Murphy, Breed</u> Mary Immaculate College, Limerick, Ireland</p> <p>All STEAMed up about Herbaria: learning from preserved plant specimens <u>McCloughlin, Thomas</u> CASTEL, Dublin City University, Ireland; DCU Herbarium and Science Archive</p> <p>Bridging the Gap between Knowledge and Action: Community, Innovation, and Sustainability Citizenship <u>Farren, Margaret; Crotty, Yvonne; Maguire, Fiona</u> Dublin City University</p>	<p>PS-G Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Examining the competence and confidence of physics teachers <u>Kozelková, Katarína¹; McLoughlin, Eilish²; Gammell, Stephen²</u> 1: Institute of Physics, Faculty of Science, Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice, Slovak Republic; 2: School of Physical Sciences, and Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning, Dublin City University, Dublin Ireland</p> <p>Instructional Vision on Entry to Initial Teacher Education <u>Nic Mhuirí, Siún^{1,2}; Kingston, Mary^{1,2}</u> 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: CASTeL</p> <p>Lab Technicians: The glue, the buffer and the boundary spanner of the Science Education Team <u>Somers, Michele</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p>	<p>PS-H Location: Room D204 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>From Capstone to Career: Navigating the Uncertainty of Open-Source Robotics in the Engineering Design Process <u>Ridgway, Leah; Jordan, Amelia Catherine</u> School of Electronic Engineering, Dublin City University, Ireland</p> <p>Educator Agency and Integrated STEAM in Early Childhood <u>Lattimore, Brenda; Gillic, Cora</u> Dublin City University, Ireland</p> <p>Doodle STEAM: Fostering Knowledge and Skills with Families Across the Lifespan. <u>Lakes, Denise; O'Reilly, Nicola</u> Childhood Development Initiative, Ireland</p>
2:05pm - 3:05pm	<p>Keynote 2: Learning to live with the world: The role of STEM education - Prof Lucy Avraamidou Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p>			
3:05pm - 3:25pm	<p>Coffee Break: Coffee Break - Day 1 Location: Room D205 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p>			
3:25pm - 4:25pm	<p>PS-I-SYM Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>The Junior Engineer Development Initiative (JEDI) <i>Chair(s): Gilligan-Lee, Katie (UCD, Ireland)</i></p> <p><i>Presentations of the Symposium</i></p> <p>Irish Primary School Children's Perceptions of Engineers and Engineering <u>Gilligan-Lee, Katie¹; Broderick, Nicola²; Broderick-Khan, Alexandra¹; Gilligan, Aisling³; Hopkins-Doyle, Aife⁴; Keenahan, Jennifer¹; Liu, Hao Lucy⁵; Quinn, Eimear¹; Wylie, Joanna¹; Buckley, Jeffrey⁶</u> ¹University College Dublin, ²DCU Institute of Education, ³ARUP, ⁴Educational Research Centre, ⁵Trinity College Dublin, ⁶Technological University of the Shannon</p> <p>Does a co-delivered teacher and engineer outreach programme (JEDI) reduce negative engineering stereotypes in primary school children? <u>Broderick-Khan, Alexandra¹; Quinn, Eimear¹; Broderick, Nicola²; Gilligan, Aisling³; Keenahan, Jennifer¹; Buckley, Jeffrey⁴; Gilligan-Lee, Katie¹</u> ¹University College Dublin, ²DCU Institute of</p>	<p>PS-J Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>FRAMING A DESIRED HUMAN SUBJECTIVITY IN STEM EDUCATION: PERSONAL AND COLLECTIVE RESPONSIBILITY FOR CARE AND JUSTICE <u>Mooney Simmie, Geraldine</u> University of Limerick, Ireland</p> <p>A collection of first-hand experiences on gender EDI policies in HE mathematics <u>Sabadin, Chiara</u> Universität Regensburg, Germany</p> <p>Investigating students' attitudes towards mathematics in socioeconomically disadvantaged schools <u>Ní Shúilleabháin, Aoibhinn¹; Delahunty, Thomas²; Hyland, Diarmaid²; Owens, Emma³; Neururer, Roisin⁴; Prendergast, Mark⁵</u> 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: Maynooth University, Ireland; 3: University of Nottingham, UK; 4: University College Dublin, Ireland; 5: University College Cork, Ireland</p>	<p>PS-K Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Lesson Study as a catalyst to promote STEM Teacher Educators' Professional Learning and Innovative Practice <u>Ryan, Mairéad; O'Dwyer, Anne; Hourigan, Mairéad; Fitzpatrick, Michelle</u> Mary Immaculate College, Ireland</p> <p>Explore, Explain, Expand - a lesson design Framework for Pre-Service STEM teachers <u>Lovatt, James; O'Neill, Natalie; Grimes, Paul; van Kampen, Paul</u> DCU CASTeL, Ireland</p> <p>Influence of industry internship on teachers preparedness for designing STEM learning experiences <u>McLoughlin, Eilish¹; Butler, Deirdre²</u> 1: School of Physical Sciences & Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning, Dublin City University, Dublin Ireland; 2: School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies & Centre for the Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning, Dublin City University, Dublin Ireland</p>	<p>PS-L Location: Room D204 (D Block St Patrick's campus)</p> <p>Innovative Pedagogies for Social Justice: Integrating Empathy, STEM, and Entrepreneurial Thinking in the EMPOWER Outreach Programme <u>Liston, Maeve; O Sullivan, Patricia; Walsh, Eleanor</u> Mary Immaculate College, Limerick, Ireland, Ireland</p> <p>Exploring the Affective Domain of Learning in Technology Education, utilising a Qualitative Modified Delphi Study. <u>Plunkett, Sheila; Dunbar, Rónán</u> Technological University of the Shannon, Ireland</p> <p>Narrative and Empathy as Engineering Design Constraints: A Mechatronics Capstone Project Case Study <u>Ridgway, Leah; McIlreavy, Gavin E.</u> School of Electronic Engineering, Dublin City University, Ireland</p>

	Education, ³ ARUP, ⁴ Technological University of the Shannon Does teachers' participation in the JEDI programme change their perceptions of engineers/engineering or their self-efficacy in delivering engineering education Quinn, Eimear¹, Broderick-Khan, Alexandra¹, Buckley, Jeffrey², Gilligan, Aisling³, Keenahan, Jennifer¹, Gilligan-Lee, Katie¹, Broderick, Nicola⁴ ¹ University College Dublin, ² Technological University of the Shannon, ³ ARUP, ⁴ DCU Institute of Education			
4:30pm - 5:30pm	PS-M Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Visualizing Potential: Design and Evaluation of a 'Voltage First' Approach to an Undergraduate Introductory Electrical Circuit Curriculum Ridgway, Leah School of Electronic Engineering, Dublin City University, Ireland Biotechnology 101: bringing 21st century Biology into secondary school laboratories Cathcart, Declan^{1,2,3} 1: Temple Carrig School.; 2: Science on Stage.; 3: Amgen Biotech Experience, Is student use of Generative AI affecting engagement with mathematics support services? Feeney, Conor; Ní Fhloinn, Eabhna Dublin City University, Ireland	PS-N Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Shaping STEM pathways through a female role model intervention Sáinz Ibáñez, Milagros¹; Gonzalez Perez, Susana²; Lopez Perez, Beatriz¹ 1: Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain; 2: CEU San Pablo, Spain Evaluating the Impact of a Role Models in pSTEM video Intervention on Post-Primary Students' Perceptions of pSTEM Ní Shuilleabháin, Aoibhinn; Smyth, Shauna; Mooney, Catherine Dublin City University, Ireland Girls, Guides and STEM: Rethinking Early Participation through Community Practice Flanagan, Bridget¹; Gillic, Cora²; Nic Mhuirí, Siún³; O'Neill, Sandra⁴ 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: Dublin City University; 3: Dublin City University, Ireland; 4: Pobal	PS-O Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Building science self-confidence among educationally disadvantaged youth: evidence from an observatory-based STEAM intervention Scully, Darina; Benbara De La Cruz, Alice Dublin City University, Ireland International study of relationship between spatial ability and attitudes to STEM by age, gender and SES Duffy, Gavin¹; Malkogeorou, Styliani¹; Pagkratidou, Marianna²; Jansen, Petra³ 1: Technological University Dublin, Ireland; 2: Dublin City University; 3: Universitat Regensburg Culturally Responsive Engineering Design Process (CREDP) for Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics(STEM) education Equity: A Comparative Literature Review of Ireland and Tamil Nadu, India Kulandaivel, Sowparnika Mary Immaculate College, Ireland	PS-P Location: Room D204 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Spatial Thinking in the Irish Primary Curriculum Nic Mhuirí, Siún; Henry, Jack; Pagkratidou, Marianna Dublin City University, Ireland From outcast to outreach: examining the effects of a spatialised STEM outreach on children's STEM motivation Roslan, Alissa; Duffy, Gavin; Zivkovic, Marija; Dorran, David Technological University Dublin, Ireland
5:30pm - 6:30pm	Film: Counted Out Location: Seamus Heaney Theatre - G114 This screening is supported by the DCU Centre for Human Rights and Citizenship Education (CHRCE), the DCU Centre for Advancement of STEM Teaching and Learning (CASTeL), and the DCU School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, and will take place as part of the CASTeL STEM Education Conference (SMEC).			
7:30pm - 10:30pm	Conference Dinner			

Friday 12th June 2026

8:30am - 9:00am	Registration - Day 2 Location: Corridor outside D203 - D205		
9:00am - 10:00am	Keynote 3: Stop 'Fixing' Girls: Evidence for a Different Approach to Gender in STEM Education - Dr Ulrika Sultan Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)		
10:05am - 11:05am	PS-Q Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus) STEM Eyes: Spatial Thinking in Primary STEM Education Nic Mhuirí, Siún^{1,2}; Langan, Angela³ 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: CASTeL; 3: Maynooth Educate Together National School Design-based Learning for Improved Spatial Skills, Creativity, and Performance in STEM Keogh, Deborah; Duffy, Gavin Technological University Dublin, Ireland An Exploration of School-Based Lesson Study as a Means of Developing Primary Teachers' Orientations Towards the Teaching of Science Boyle, Mary; Murphy, Cliona; Dooley, Thérèse CASTeL, Dublin City University, Ireland	PS-R-SYM Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus) The Hare's Corner in the Classroom: The Role of STEM Education in Addressing the Biodiversity Crisis <i>Chair(s): Ni Shuilleabhain, Aoibhinn (DCU, Ireland)</i> <i>Presentations of the Symposium</i> The Effect of STEM policy on Nature Education at Post Primary Level – a case of Economy vs Ecology O'Neill, Natalie DCU Minding the gap in botanical education – working with Pre-service Biology Teachers to Counteract Plant Blindness Kerr, Karen QUB, Belfast Where is nature in primary STEM Education? Kelly, Orla DCU, Ireland	PS-S Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Advocating, Applying, and Advancing Learning: Teachers' Roles in Out-of-School STEM Education Augusthian, Priva Dharshini¹; Kelly, Orla¹; Lovatt, James¹; McCarthy, Jack² 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: The Rediscovery Centre, Ireland (Re)Directing Attention, Embodying (In)Justice: Forum Theatre and Attentive Love in Science Teacher Education Torres Olave, Betzabe University of Groningen, Netherlands, The Unlearning Modernity: Remaking Science Education in the Anthropocene Hurley, Mairéad¹; Achiam, Marianne² 1: Trinity Science & Society Research Centre, School of Education, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland; 2: Department of Science Education, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

11:05am - 11:25am	Coffee Break - Day 2: Coffee Break - Day 2 Location: Room D205 (D Block St Patrick's campus)		
11:25am - 12:25pm	PS-T Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Building Resilience through Partnership: The Role of Professional Learning Leaders in Primary Integrated STEM. Moynihan, Denis; McMorrough, Anne Dublin City University Institute of Education, Ireland Leveraging the History of Mathematics to Foster Inclusivity, Engagement, and Understanding in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics: Exploring the Practices and Perspectives of Irish Post-Primary Mathematics Teachers Begley, Stephen; Hyland, Diarmaid; Mac an Bhairst, Ciarán Maynooth University, Ireland Pride and Inspiration: Reigniting the spark in early career researchers O'Donoghue, John Trinity College Dublin, Ireland	PS-U Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Does going digital change the clock? Comparing an online and paper-based algebra assessment. O'Brien, Aoife Atlantic Technological University, Ireland Understanding Ireland's Performance in Measurement and Geometry: Insights from TIMSS 2023 McHugh, Grainne; Grimes, Paul; Venkat, Hamsa Dublin City University Developing R Shiny Apps for Teaching Time Series in a Postgraduate Statistics Program Cabero del Hierro, Andrea; Howard, Emma Trinity College Dublin, Ireland	PS-V Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Checking for Understanding or Supporting New Learning? Teachers' Use of Retrieval-Based Methodologies in Mathematics Long, Eoghan; Ni Riordáin, Máire; Prendergast, Mark University College Cork, Ireland Youth facilitators' mathematical knowledge Venkat, Hamsa¹; Bowie, Lynn²; Mukuka, Angel¹ 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: OLICO Mathematics Education Primary Teachers' Mapping of Additive Word Problems to Number Sentences Mukuka, Angel¹; Bowie, Lynn²; Venkat, Hamsa¹ 1: Dublin City University, Ireland; 2: University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
12:25pm - 1:10pm	Lunch - Day 2 Location: Staffroom/Quad (Outside area)		
1:10pm - 2:10pm	PS-W Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Curricular Reform: Considering the role of the growth mindset of Curriculum leaders, through the lens of the Primary Mathematics curriculum (PMC) 2023. Waters, Orla Mary Immaculate College Limerick, Ireland A Ripple Effect: Co-Designing Youth-Focused Cybersecurity Education for Multi-Generational Impact Cronin, Moya; O'Keeffe, Michelle; Sheil, Ashley; Camilleri, Jacob; Gruben, Melanie; Calnan, Elaine; Ryan-Duffy, Anne; Murray, Hazel Munster Technological University, Ireland 'STEAM from the Start': A Human-centred Framework for Sustainable STEAM Integration in Early Childhood Education Walshe, Paula Dundalk Institute of Technology	PS-X Location: Theatre D211 (D Block St Patrick's campus) Supporting STEM Learning Through a Collaborative Community Partnership Ryan, Mairead; O'Dwyer, Anne; Liston, Maeve; Walsh, Eleanor Mary Immaculate College, Ireland DreamBig: Building STEM Identity through Regional Education/Industry Partnerships Dunbar, Ronan; Leacy, Ross; Mordan, Cairiona TUS, Ireland Identifying Local Strengths to Build Community STEM Capital and STEM Participation Hall-Dadson, Jane¹; Beasy, Kim¹; Fraser, Sharon¹; Cirkony, Connie² 1: University of Tasmania, Australia; 2: Monash University, Australia	PS-Y Location: Room D203 (D Block St Patrick's campus) "I wouldn't have thought about the science. I didn't realise half of what was going on!" - Sociodramatic co-play as a pedagogical approach for early STEM learning. O'Reilly, Nicola DCU, Ireland Student Co-Created Formative Assessment in a Cross-Disciplinary Data Literacy Module: A Microcurricula Approach at Scale Abgaz, Yalemisew Dublin City University, Ireland Do We Keep Asking the Same Questions and Expect Different Answers? Advancing Adaptive Mathematics Assessment through Educational Robotics Al Omoush, Muhammad H.; Ward, Monica School of Computing, Dublin City University, Ireland
2:15pm - 3:15pm	Closing Location: Theatre D210 (D Block St Patrick's campus)		

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Student Co-Created Formative Assessment in a Cross-Disciplinary Data Literacy Module: A Microcurricula Approach at Scale

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Abstract

Designing inclusive and engaging formative assessments at scale across heterogeneous programmes remains a persistent challenge in higher education (Andersson & Palm, 2017; King, 2022). This challenge is amplified as data literacy and analytics emerge as critical transversal competencies across all disciplines in an AI-shaped graduate landscape (Reynolds et al., 2020). Yet instructor-designed assessments dominate at scale, lacking student perspective and inclusivity. To our knowledge, no prior study has examined student co-creation of formative assessment within a cross-disciplinary microcurricula framework at institutional scale. This paper presents a co-creation intervention within a microcurricula module (a modular cross-faculty design serving 15+ programmes across five faculties) in which high-performing students from the previous cohort co-designed formative assessments, enabling prospective students to learn directly from peer strategies and experience. These were offered as optional preparation resources for summative assessment across seven Data Literacy and Analytics Topics (Abgaz, 2026; Abgaz & Dunne, 2023) with this research focusing on two practice-heavy, technology-oriented topics. Among 1,432 and 1,387 enrolled students per topic, 392 and 216 respectively engaged with the co-created assessments. Independent samples t-tests revealed a statistically significant improvement ($p < .05$) across both topics. Thematic analysis of student feedback further revealed enhanced metacognitive awareness and increased confidence in assessment preparedness, reinforcing the value of peer-designed resources in cross-disciplinary learning. These findings position student co-created formative assessment as a scalable, equity-aligned strategy for cross-disciplinary STEM education. In doing so, they reposition students as active agents and co-owners of the learning process, with implications for equitable curriculum design across higher education.

Keywords: Student co-creation, Interdisciplinary Education, Formative Assessment innovation

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Do We Keep Asking the Same Questions and Expect Different Answers? Advancing Adaptive Mathematics Assessment through Educational Robotics

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Abstract

Understanding how assessment practices represent the diversity of students' mathematical abilities is essential for promoting inclusive primary education. Standardised assessments provide consistent measurement conditions across learners (Rear, 2018; Sireci, 2020), supporting comparability of outcomes, while adaptive assessment approaches offer complementary mechanisms for examining performance through personalised task pathways aligned with shared curriculum standards (Vie et al., 2017). This study examines how robot-based assessment environments can enhance adaptive mathematics assessment by generating engagement and performance data and capturing students' interaction patterns and achievement outcomes.

This study presents findings from research with a cohort of primary school students with dyslexia. As part of the study, an educational robot was co-designed with the participants, their teachers, and an educational expert. It was then used in informal mathematics assessment activities focusing on geometry, numerical reasoning, and problem-solving. Interaction logs and observational measures were collected to examine how students demonstrated competence across mathematical skill areas during interactive sessions. Performance profiles derived from the robot-based environment were compared with paper-based assessment results to examine how different assessment formats represent students' demonstrated abilities.

The comparison between robot and paper-based assessment results revealed variation in student performance across the previously identified mathematical areas. In the robot-based activities, some students showed stronger performance in visual-spatial tasks involving 2D/3D shapes, reflecting strengths in visual and manipulation tasks, while others demonstrated stronger outcomes in analytical and multi-step reasoning activities. These patterns could potentially inform differentiated learner performance profiles, supporting teachers in identifying strengths and areas requiring additional support. In contrast, paper-based assessment results focused mainly on overall scores,

providing a less detailed representation of domain-specific performance patterns. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of robot-based, data-informed assessment environments to support more responsive and inclusive mathematics assessment practices in primary education.

Keywords: Mathematics, Adaptive assessment, Robot-based assessment, Dyslexia

Acknowledgements

This work was conducted with the financial support of the Research Ireland Centre for Research Training in Digitally-Enhanced Reality (d-real) under Grant No. 18/CRT/6224. For the purpose of Open Access, the author has applied a CC BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

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Advocating, Applying, and Advancing Learning: Teachers' Roles in Out-of-School STEM Education

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Abstract

Out-of-school learning experiences play an important role in fostering curiosity, critical thinking and career interest in STEM-related fields (Dabney et al., 2012). Teacher participation and engagement before, during, and after out-of-school trips enhance the learning experience of students (Behrendt & Franklin, 2014). This presentation explores the role of teachers in out-of-school STEM education through the perspective of the education team of the Rediscovery Centre (RDC), Ireland's National Centre for the Circular Economy (CE). The RDC delivers around 600-700 workshops annually, serving a wide variety of students and teachers, thus providing valuable outsider perspectives on the role of teachers in STEM and CE education.

This study uses a change theory approach with an appreciative inquiry lens, analysed using the Miles and Huberman method through cycles of data reduction, display and validation. Appreciative inquiry focuses on the programme's strengths and 'best moments,' to enable growth without a deficit-based 'problem-solving' lens (Cooperrider et al., 2008).

Drawing on interview and focus group data from out-of-school educators in the RDC, this presentation addresses a key theme that emerged from the analysis: the role of teachers in supporting student learning through the education programme. The tentative findings indicate how out-of-school educators view the role of teachers before, after and during out-of-school learning. This led to the development of a few teacher archetypes- for example, 'ideal teachers' play a role as 'advocates' for student well-being, 'applying' activities in school to relate with CE ideas, and 'advancing' learning from the centre in classes back at school. By identifying teachers as advocates who support and extend learning beyond out-of-school workshops, the findings emphasise the human element necessary to broaden participation in out-of-school STEM, sustainability, and CE education. Thereby, we highlight and situate teachers as central to the human infrastructure that sustains learning beyond isolated out-of-school learning events.

Keywords: Teacher, STEM education, out-of-school education

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Leveraging the History of Mathematics to Foster Inclusivity, Engagement, and Understanding in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics: Exploring the Practices and Perspectives of Irish Post-Primary Mathematics Teachers.

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Abstract

Over the past six decades, mathematics education researchers have called for greater examination and measurement of the role and value of the history of mathematics (HoM) in teaching and learning. HoM is acknowledged as a motivator for learners, creating pathways for developing understanding and problem-solving skills, giving rise to metacognitive learning opportunities, whilst enriching mathematics with a sense of purpose and wonder (Clark, 2019). It provides opportunities for learners to experience mathematics through a diverse lens; from historical accounts of concept/idea development, to sharing the diverse ways a problem may be solved/represented, and showcasing of the nature of mathematics (Fauvel, 1991). Furthermore, it provides space to discuss social justice within mathematics and democratise STEM; a space not traditionally celebrated throughout Western societies' mathematical history. Ultimately, HoM celebrates and promotes the human side of mathematics - that mathematics has culturally and socially evolved, and that it belongs to everyone.

In Ireland, the current landscape regarding the HoM in secondary education is unreported. The aim of this research is to examine how HoM can act as a gateway towards inclusivity, engagement and understanding in the classroom. This research will frame the Irish context by assessing teacher and teacher-trainer's engagement levels with HoM; voicing the perspectives of Irish teachers and teacher-trainers relating to HoM; leveraging HoM to further democratise STEM and promote diversity representation; developing curriculum resources; and measuring the impact of HoM on student motivation, engagement, and appreciation of mathematics. Following a mixed-methods approach, a systematic literature review, surveys and interviews/focus groups with key stakeholders, and pre-imposed testing of curriculum resources will provide rich datasets to address the research's aim and objectives. Informed by constructivist theory and the Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching Framework (Nolan et al., 2015), this oral presentation will provide an update on this research in progress.

Keywords: History of Mathematics, Humanising Mathematics; Democratising STEM

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An Exploration of School-Based Lesson Study as a Means of Developing Primary Teachers' Inquiry Orientation Towards the Teaching of Science

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Abstract

Research highlights several concerns regarding the teaching and learning of primary science in Ireland, including a need for increased levels of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) and Subject Matter Knowledge (SMK) among teachers, as well as greater use of Inquiry Based Science Education methodologies (Murphy et al., 2023). This presentation arises from a doctoral study which explored the use of school-based Lesson Study (LS) as a means of developing primary teachers' orientations towards the teaching of science, an overarching aspect of PCK in science (Magnusson et al., 1999). Although Magnusson et al. (1999) identify differing orientations that teachers may have, inquiry orientation, which aims to represent science as inquiry and leads the teacher to support students in defining and investigating problems, is the area of focus in this presentation.

Data were collected across three cycles of LS. LS meeting audio recordings, teachers' individual reflective logs and collaboratively designed Teaching and Learning Plans were examined for references to an inquiry orientation to teaching science. These references were subsequently analysed based on an emergent framework which reflected varying types of inquiry identified by Banchi and Bell (2008), Cuevas et al. (2005) and Magnusson et al. (1999). The framework was utilised to evaluate any change in teachers' inquiry orientations as a result of participation in LS. Findings reveal that LS supported both the development of teachers' inquiry orientations and SMK, which combined, positively impacted children's learning. A further novel feature of this research study is that it provides an expanded conceptualisation of inquiry orientation towards the teaching of science. This study highlights school-based LS as an effective CPL methodology for the development of teachers' inquiry orientation towards science, which is particularly pertinent at this time of curriculum change.

Keywords: Lesson Study, Primary Science, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Inquiry Orientation.

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Fostering critical thinking in mathematics through analysing reasoning tasks

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Abstract

It is generally accepted that teaching in both secondary and higher education institutions - in all subjects, including mathematics - should go beyond the transmission of knowledge to involve the development of higher order skills such as critical thinking (Saroyan, 2022). But, although critical thinking is often highlighted in national educational policies and qualification standards, there is little indication that this translates into practice (Saroyan, 2022). This is increasingly important today to enable citizens to make informed decisions in the face of growing levels of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity.. Empowering students to navigate through uncertainty becomes even more crucial given the rapid progress of generative artificial intelligence and the resultant concern that students might accept generated responses without questioning (Pepin et al., 2025).

We assert that tasks we label 'analysing reasoning' tasks - which provide opportunities for students to make decisions about the correctness of a given piece of mathematics - are ideally suited to the development of the core critical thinking skills of analysis, evaluation and inference (Facione, 1990), in mathematics. Engaging with such 'analysing reasoning' tasks requires students to (i) check assumptions and/or detect bias; (ii) query claims; (iii) identify errors; or (iv) compare solution methods/arguments, thereby allowing difficulties and misconceptions to be confronted rather than avoided. However, the prevalence of

such tasks in textbooks seems very low as evidenced by findings presented here. Each of 1688 tasks from four undergraduate Calculus and Analysis textbooks was examined and classified as an 'analysing reasoning' task only if it afforded opportunities to critique a reasoning sequence presented in the task via any of (i)-(iv) above. To address this gap, we propose a set of principles to facilitate the design of analysing reasoning tasks. We plan to trial and evaluate tasks we design using these principles through think-aloud task-based interviews.

Keywords: critical thinking, mathematics education, task design

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Developing R Shiny Apps for Teaching Time Series in a Postgraduate Statistics Program

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Abstract

R Shiny apps are a web application framework that was launched and implemented in R Studio in 2012 that allows the creation of apps using the R language. These apps offer the opportunity to promote active learning and understand abstract statistical concepts through simulations, making learning more dynamic and engaging than traditional learning. However, most of the R Shiny apps available for teaching statistics focus on fundamental statistical and probability concepts, but there are few Time Series-specific apps that explore core concepts in detail [1-3]. In addition, there is a limited evaluation of their impact on student learning and outcomes. This is crucial to identify which aspects of the R Shiny apps are beneficial to learning and which aspects should be incorporated into future apps. For this reason, the purpose of this project was to design, implement, and evaluate a set of R Shiny apps specifically designed for the Time Series module

taught in the Postgraduate Statistics and Data Science program at Trinity College Dublin. In total 13 R Shiny apps were developed. Apps followed a similar design and included relevant theory, visual interactive elements and quizzes. A survey was implemented, combining student feedback with knowledge-based questions to determine whether, by using these apps, the students have achieved the learning outcomes and improved their understanding of the material. Although the survey had a low response rate, the results showed that the participants rated the apps positively, especially the interactive visualisations, which helped them understand the abstract concepts of the module. Furthermore, the average score on the knowledge questions was 4.6 out of 8, indicating a relatively solid understanding of the syllabus. In conclusion, R Shiny apps have the potential to complement traditional and online teaching.

Keywords: R Shiny, active learning, Statistics education

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Biotechnology 101: bringing 21st-century biology into secondary school laboratories

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Abstract

A practical biotechnology laboratory course was developed as a 20-hour, 10-week module. In this inquiry-based learning (IBL) module, students learn actively through a structured problem-based learning (PBL) approach: this is particularly relevant to teachers in the context of current senior cycle curriculum reform in secondary level Biology in Ireland. This hybrid pedagogy combines the guided inquiry approach of gaining knowledge and understanding through a scaffolded investigation, with the application of knowledge and skills to solve a presented, defined problem. Skills are learned as needed to move towards a solution, while fundamental biological concepts such as cell division, DNA replication, and gene expression are explored and appreciated

in the context of hands-on authentic investigations in real-world scenarios designed to provide relevance and student ownership. Learning techniques in microbiology, DNA profiling, PCR and genetic engineering, students develop practical skills and core knowledge in molecular biology through the lens of technology, sustainability and the environment.

Mathematics plays a central role in this module, stressing the importance of both numeracy skills and scientific literacy in laboratory investigations in the life sciences.

Labs were initially piloted with Irish and Dutch students, one cohort from disadvantaged schools, another of gifted students. The author will give an account of the evolution of these modules, supported by Amgen Biotech Experience and Science on Stage, through international collaboration and action research in Ireland, the Netherlands, Switzerland and the United Kingdom.

Keywords: Problem-solving, Inquiry, Secondary, Biotechnology

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Integrating AI-enabled Indicators in Adapting the Rubric for Assessing Project-Based Learning with Digital Technologies

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Abstract

Background: Project-Based Learning (PBL) supported by digital technologies is a cornerstone of constructionist pedagogy (Papert, 1980). For over a decade, a large-scale, philanthropy-funded field research project has implemented this approach in state-run middle and secondary schools across India (xxx, 2022). While a rubric for assessing student-led digital artefacts was validated in 2019 (xxx, 2019), the emergence of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) necessitated its revision. This paper presents the adaptation of the 2019 rubric to assess students' integration of GenAI in research and

inquiry processes, incorporating parameters for analysing prompt complexity and ethical AI attribution.

Method: The rubric underwent iterative refinement through multiple rounds of feedback from PBL experts and project facilitators. Experts reviewed the indicators for clarity, relevance, and alignment with PBL principles, leading to revisions that improved clarity, reduced overlap, and assessed relevance of AI use indicators. A pilot study was conducted with pre-service teachers and graduate students (M.A. in Education and Technology) at a deemed university in India to test the revised rubric. Participants used this rubric to evaluate projects, and the resulting data were analysed for inter-rater reliability (IRR).

Results: Expert feedback led to the refinement of nine core indicators (e.g., authentic learning, knowledge deepening) of the earlier rubric. Specifically, sharpening the AI-integrated indicators related to quality of the prompts and acknowledgment of the AI use. The paper further reports the challenges with establishing inter-rater reliability of the new rubric, the work in progress of further validating and improving the IRR.

Keywords: PBL with Technology, assessing PBL, AI indicators in PBL rubric, constructivist digital pedagogies

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A Ripple Effect: Co-Designing Youth-Focused Cybersafety Education for Multi-Generational Impact

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Abstract

Young people aged 12–18 occupy a paradoxical position in the evolving digital landscape. While 94% of Irish children aged 8–12 own a smart device, and are perceived as highly tech-literate, 25% experience online grooming, scams, or harassment (CyberSafeKids, 2024). The UN Committee on the Rights of the Child has also

highlighted digital literacy as a core educational priority, encompassing AI misinformation, online persuasion, and data surveillance (Children's Rights Alliance, 2025).

As young people are relied upon to act as informal digital mediators for families and peers, this research explores how gamified learning approaches can foster positive engagement with best practice cybersecurity and responsible digital citizenship. Preliminary findings from participatory focus groups (n=18, aged 12–18) conducted across two sessions held with fourth to sixth year students, online and in person, inform the co-design of a proposed gamified e-learning cybersafety course. Using thematic analysis, focus groups explored young people's lived digital experiences, perceived cybersafety needs, and their preferences for both individual learning and knowledge transfer to family members and communities.

Findings revealed that participants actively mediate digital life for parents and grandparents, including identifying scams, navigating misinformation such as AI-generated deepfakes, and managing account security. Participants also distinguished between age-differentiated risks, pointing to grooming and cyberbullying as youth-specific concerns, and financial scams as more prevalent among older adults. Overall, priority learning topics included phishing, password management, AI literacy, and platform-specific scams targeting all ages. Preferred learning formats included short 15–30 minute animated chapters, minigames with competitive mechanics, and scenario-based activities. Participants expressed motivation to share their learnings through peer award showcases, supported by printable facilitation resources and quizzes.

These findings inform the structure of a forthcoming cybersafety course positioning young people as both learners and community educators, aligned with Ireland's Digital Strategy for Schools (Department of Education, 2026).

Keywords: Cyber safety education, Co-design, Community resilience, Young people, Digital Divide

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International study of relationship between spatial ability and attitudes to STEM by age, gender and SES

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Abstract

Research has shown the importance of cognitive and affective factors in choosing a career in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) with academic performance significantly related to positive attitudes to STEM (Pinxten et al., 2014) and spatial ability (Wai et al., 2009). The purpose of this study was to examine how spatial ability is related to STEM attitudes and how this relationship varies with age, gender and socioeconomic status (SES) in two different countries – Greece and Ireland. Following ethical approval, participants were recruited from two grade levels – 6 and 10 (6th class of primary school and 4th year of secondary school in Ireland) - in schools in Ireland and Greece. A total of 763 pupils participated (Greece: grade 6, n=270, grade 10, n=421; Ireland: grade 6, n=27, grade 10, n=45). Each completed two tests of spatial ability – the Paper Folding Test (PFT, Ekstrom et al., 1976) and the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA, Thurstone, 1973)– and two surveys – a sociodemographic/SES and Student Attitudes towards STEM.

Attitudes towards STEM decreased significantly with grade level for Greece ($t(689) = 2.61, p = .009, d = 0.21$) but not Ireland. There was a significant increase in scores on both tests of spatial ability from grades 6 to 10 in both countries. A significant difference was found in favour of males in Attitudes towards Engineering and Technology for participants from Greece (Kruskal-Wallis $H(2) = 43.13, p < .001, f = .25$) but not Ireland. For both countries, there were no gender differences in attitudes towards Maths and Science. A gender difference in favour of females in the PFT was found for both Greece (Kruskal-Wallis $H(2) = 8.50, p = .014, f = .08$) and Ireland ($F(2, 69) = 3.39, p = .039, \eta^2 = .09$) but there was no gender difference in PMA scores. With respect to SES, there was a significant increase in Attitudes towards STEM with SES for Greece (one-way ANOVA with three SES levels, $F(2, 590) = 21.02, p < .001, \eta^2 = .067$) but not Ireland. Scores on both tests of spatial ability were found to significantly increase with SES for Greece (Kruskal-Wallis $H(2) = 27.70, p < .001, f = .20$) but not Ireland. For both countries, STEM attitudes were significantly related to spatial ability with a larger correlation measured for Ireland (for Greece, $\rho = .283, p < .001$; for Ireland, $r = .467, p < .001$).

Keywords: STEM education, STEM attitudes, Spatial ability, Gender, SES

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DreamBig: Building STEM Identity through Regionally Focused Education & Industry Partnerships

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Abstract

The DreamBig programme is a regional STEM education initiative designed to broaden participation, strengthen learner agency, and foster inclusive pathways into STEM careers and further study. Developed through collaboration between the Advanced Technology in Manufacturing cluster, Technological University of the Shannon, secondary schools, and manufacturing industry partners in Ireland's Midlands region, the programme responds to persistent challenges in STEM engagement, particularly among students with limited exposure to STEM role models, authentic learning contexts, and visible career pathways. This project presents the design framework, implementation approach, and emerging evaluation insights from DreamBig, positioning it as a model for inclusive, community-based STEM education.

The study is guided by three evaluation questions: how do teachers interpret and implement DreamBig resources and partnership activities; what forms of student engagement and learning are perceived through participation; and what design features appear to support inclusive STEM identity development in regional education–industry partnerships? The initiative integrates three core elements: contextualised classroom learning linked to real-world STEM applications, engagement with industry professionals to highlight the people and identities behind STEM practice, and collaborative partnerships between educators, learners, industry, and community stakeholders.

Through teacher training, career-focused learning resources, multimedia materials showcasing regional STEM professionals, and a student-led Innovation Challenge, the programme aims to support learners' sense of agency, belonging, and future orientation in STEM.

Using a design-based research approach, the study examines teachers' responses to DreamBig resources and partnership activities, focusing on how educators implement industry-informed materials and interpret student engagement. Data sources include teacher reflections, classroom implementation feedback, educator observations, and end-of-year Innovation Challenge Expo feedback gathered at TUS in May 2026 from 12 teachers across 11 schools and 38 participating students. Early findings indicate that teachers perceived the programme as supporting more inclusive classroom environments, increased student confidence, teamwork, communication, independent learning, and prototype development. Teachers particularly valued the open-ended and student-led nature of the challenge, which enabled learners to pursue personally meaningful and locally relevant problems. Student feedback reinforced these themes, identifying collaboration, idea generation, CAD/CAM, robotics, C++, 3D printing, prototyping, manufacturing site visits, and presenting final designs as meaningful aspects of the experience.

The study contributes a practice-informed framework for strengthening inclusive STEM participation through teacher-supported identity development, authentic industry engagement, and regional collaboration. Future work aims to further examine the transferability and adaptability of the DreamBig model across other STEM communities seeking to connect schools, learners, and industry in ways that are equitable, contextualised, and socially meaningful.

Keywords: *STEM identity, inclusive STEM education, education–industry partnerships, learner agency, regional STEM collaboration*

Bridging the Gap between Knowledge and Action: Community, Innovation, and Sustainability Citizenship

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Abstract

The EU BRIDGES Policy Experimentation Action (2025-2028) is about *teaching for Sustainability Citizenship* (SC). It builds on the SYNAPSES Teacher Academy project: Empowering educators for Teaching on SC (2023-2026). BRIDGES whole-school approaches to SC ensures that it becomes embedded into every aspect of school operations. It posits that to enable young people to act as sustainability citizens, schools need to work as eco-social systems in which knowledge, attitudes and behaviors are formed through real and community-connected practices. As proposed by Bevan (2016), a learning ecology is the physical, social, and cultural context in which learning takes place (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Learning Ecology

The key learning ecologies identified by BRIDGES include Classroom Learning, Whole-School Learning Ecology, and Open-Schooling / Living-Lab Partnerships. In such eco-social systems, sustainability and citizenship are interconnected.

GreenComp (EU, 2022) sets out 12 competences, grouped into four areas: Embodying sustainability values, Embracing complexity, Envisioning sustainable futures, and Acting for a sustainable future. SC can bridge the knowledge-action gap (Bujold et al. 2020; Colombo et al. 2023) by integrating GreenComp into the three dimensions of Thinking, Acting and Being thus transforming sustainability into a lived practice.

Thinking means understanding environmental challenges. Acting is about citizens actively contributing to sustainable societies. Being is based on the values of responsibility, participation, solidarity and justice. Developing students' place within today's learning ecologies begins with helping them recognise that they are ecological beings living in a constantly changing world.

The BRIDGES Activity Design Cycle consists of five iterative phases – Inquiry (Initial Problem Definition), Co-Design, Action (Application), Analysis (Reflection), and Sharing (Transfer) & Next Steps - each corresponding to one or more Sustainability Citizenship competence strands (Thinking – Acting – Being). The Bridges portal (<https://portal.project-bridges.eu/good-practices>) will provide a means of sharing innovative pedagogies and practices.

In this presentation, we will demonstrate the innovative practices proposed to date that promote the development of Sustainability Citizenship in different educational settings based on Thinking, Acting and Being.

Keywords: Sustainability Citizenship. Learning Ecologies. Challenge Based Learning.

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Is student use of Generative AI affecting engagement with mathematics support services?

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Abstract

Mathematics learning support (MLS) has been shown to improve student retention and performance in mathematics in higher education both in Ireland (Jacobs & Ní Fhloinn, 2019) and internationally (Lawson, Grove & Croft, 2020). However, since the university campus closures in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, MLS practitioners have reported lower engagement by students (Gilbert et al, 2025). In Spring 2025, we undertook a study into the usage of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) by undergraduate students studying at least one mathematics module in an Irish university.

One of our research questions was to explore whether students were using GenAI in place of freely-available MLS services in the university, whether through a drop-in centre for in-person support, or individual online appointments with tutors. We also investigated the reasons that students gave for using GenAI or MLS for additional help with their mathematics module. We found that an overwhelming 91% of students were using GenAI for mathematics, and that almost a third of those had first used GenAI for this purpose in the previous three months. However, we found no evidence to support the hypothesis that students were using GenAI in place of MLS. There was a very weak positive correlation between frequency of usage of GenAI for maths and frequency of use of MLS, but it was not statistically significant. Many of the reasons given for the use of GenAI overlapped with those given for the use of MLS, but there were particular exceptions to this, as will be discussed.

Keywords: Generative artificial intelligence, mathematics support, higher education

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Using Japanese Lesson Study in Initial Teacher Education to Support Primary STEM for Planetary Health

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Abstract

STEM education plays a transformative role in shaping informed, ethical, and action-oriented responses to 21st-century challenges. In Ireland, the introduction of the new primary STEM curriculum necessitates an urgent shift toward integrated approaches that empower learners to address real-world challenges. While connections across STEM disciplines are not new, supporting teachers to design and enact coherent, interdisciplinary learning experiences remains a significant challenge within existing structures of teacher education (Fitzpatrick et al., 2026; Wieselmann et al., 2025).

The SPARK project, funded by Research Ireland, responds to this challenge through a school-university partnership involving six primary teachers, 27 preservice teachers, and teacher educators. Japanese Lesson Study provides the organising framework for professional learning, selected for its robust, research-based, and iterative process of collaborative planning, classroom implementation, guided observation, and reflection, which focuses specifically on enhancing student learning (Lewis & Takahashi, 2013). Within this framework, participants co-created STEM inquiry units, rooted in planetary health and action, focused on applying STEM knowledge to environmental challenges.

A critical component of SPARK is the use of “data for the planet” where children engage with both primary and secondary datasets, including historical climate data to support evidence-based reasoning. Through scientific inquiry and digital tools, students developed early systems thinking and engaged in age-appropriate forms of informed decision-making. Such approaches align with growing emphasis on developing STEM capabilities through authentic, data-rich learning experiences (Makar et al., 2023).

This paper presents findings from the first cycle of SPARK (Spring 2026), analysing six research lessons. The analysis highlights the tensions and affordances of interdisciplinary STEM teaching for planetary health, particularly in relation to teacher decision-making, integration of data practices, and the pedagogical demands of working with young learners. Implications for initial teacher education and professional development are discussed, emphasising how collaborative, research-engaged pedagogies can bridge the gap between STEM knowledge and meaningful environmental action.

Keywords: Integrated STEM education, Socio-scientific problems, School-university partnership

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Girls, Guides and STEM: Rethinking Early Participation through Community Practice

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Abstract

Gendered perceptions of competence in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) frequently emerge in early childhood. This developmental period offers a critical opportunity for carefully designed STEM experiences to counter marginalisation and challenge gender-based stereotypes about who belongs in these fields (Fleer, 2021). Situated within the theme Inclusive Communities & Identity in Education, this project examines how community-based, girl-centred STEM experiences can support identity formation and agency among girls aged 5–7 within the Irish Girl Guides, while also engaging Ladybird leaders and Senior Branch members as co-facilitators and role models.

The study adopts a design-informed, collaborative inquiry approach. A needs analysis with organisational leadership and pre-intervention questionnaires with Ladybird leaders and Senior Branch members informs professional learning designed to strengthen leaders' STEM self-efficacy and pedagogical confidence. Educator beliefs and confidence significantly influence children's engagement and dispositions (DeJarnette, 2018). By positioning leaders as collaborative co-facilitators, the project broadens participation through female role modelling and shared leadership.

Children engage in playful, inquiry-based engineering challenges using LEGO, structured iterative design cycles (ask–imagine–plan–create–improve), and intentional use of spatial and problem-solving language. These approaches foster agency, collaboration and persistence while normalising STEM as creative and socially meaningful (González-Pérez et al., 2020).

Findings from the needs analysis, pre-questionnaires and initial implementation day will be presented. The project advances a conceptual model linking early identity formation, leader self-efficacy and community-based STEM practice. It argues that broadening participation requires cultivating inclusive, community-based learning environments where girls experience themselves and see others like them, as capable STEM changemakers.

Keywords: STEM Education, gender, community-based learning

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Design of an inquiry-based learning laboratory on concepts of earth and space

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Abstract

Research has shown that misconceptions about basic astronomy phenomena are common amongst the general population and that many adults cannot construct scientific explanations for observable astronomical phenomena (Plummer, 2014). With this in mind, the introduction of the earth and space strand as part of the revised Junior Cycle science curriculum in 2017 was a welcome development. Lack of understanding has been attributed to underdeveloped spatial reasoning and traditional instruction (Plummer, 2014). Rivet and Kastens (2012) reported that the use of physical models supports learners to visualise celestial motion, by reducing cognitive load.

This paper describes the design of a three-hour, guided-inquiry laboratory aimed at supporting learners to visualise a number of earth-sun phenomena, including the daily path of the sun and stars, climate regions and earth's seasons. Learners manipulate a bespoke, 3D-printed, celestial-sphere model to complete their inquiries and make connections between different representations (e.g. 2D diagrams, mathematical equations). Design of the 3D model and accompanying inquiry tasks are discussed in terms of how they address recognised learning barriers (e.g. perspective taking). Challenges of the design, the limitations of the 3D model and the potential for the laboratory to support learning at post-primary level (and beyond) are discussed.

Keywords: earth and space, spatial reasoning, inquiry-based learning

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Symposium: The Junior Engineer Development Initiative (JEDI)

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Abstract

In Ireland, and internationally, there are substantial disparities in the profile of people who study engineering in second and third level education (Higher Education Authority, 2023). More specifically, females and those from lower SES backgrounds are disproportionately under-represented. As the role of engineers has evolved from being technical experts to being key agents in shaping the future of industries, communities, and the environment (National Academy of Engineering, 2004), there is increasing need to ensure that the engineering community reflects the diversity of the modern workforce. This raises the question as to why individuals from particular backgrounds, do not pursue careers in engineering, and how we can address this? In this symposium, we endeavour to address these questions by presenting results from three interconnected studies that were each conducted through a Research Ireland grant titled the *Junior Engineer Development Initiative (JEDI)*. This symposium consequently aligns closely with the conference theme of Inclusive Communities and Identity in Education.

In the first presentation, findings are presented on primary school children's perceptions of engineers and engineering. This includes both physical and target (trait) characteristics. The results are the first such benchmarks from primary school children in Ireland and provide important insights into children's misconceptions about engineers and engineering. The findings provide valuable information on children's identity and agency with respect to engineering.

Expanding on study 1, the second presentation outlines a novel intervention, the Junior Engineer Development Initiative. This is a programme for 5th and 6th class students. It is designed to improve children's engineering skills and understanding of the attributes needed to be an engineer, and to address negative stereotypes of engineers and engineering. This study aligns with the theme of broadening participation as the intervention focuses on broadening participation in engineering, particularly in women and those from lower SES backgrounds. The programme also directly aims to improve children's identity as "STEM people".

In study 3, the theme aligns with the strand of collaborative inquiry. This study explores the benefits of participation in the JEDI programme for classroom teachers. JEDI is a co-delivered programme in which teachers and professional engineers work collaboratively to deliver engineering outreach. This study highlights one model for classrooms and communities to work together. This study also aligns with the strand of identity and agency as it reports changes in how teachers view themselves as "STEM people" through their engineering self-efficacy.

We propose that children's a) perceptions of engineers, and b) understanding of the skills/attributes needed to be an engineer, are contributing factors influencing their interest in learning engineering and following Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) careers more generally. Across this symposium, we first establish baseline benchmarks of these perceptions. Second, a novel intervention is proposed (the JEDI programme) to improve children's perceptions and finally, the importance of the teacher-engineer partnership in the efficacy of engineering outreach (the JEDI programme) is highlighted.

Keywords: Junior Engineer Development Initiative, engineering outreach, intervention co-delivery, primary school STEM

Paper 1: Irish Primary School Children's Perceptions of Engineers and Engineering

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Abstract

Stereotypes are commonly held, often oversimplified perceptions of a particular type of person/group of people. These include stereotypes of both physical and target characteristics. Gender stereotypes significantly influence career choices as engineers are often stereotyped as male and/or a tradesperson/mechanic (Buckley et al., 2023). However, beyond physical characteristics, no research has explored perceptions of engineers' target characteristics. Furthermore, stereotypes vary based on cultural specifications and age. No prior research has explored children's perceptions of engineers in Ireland.

In this study we investigate whether perceptions of engineers' physical and target characteristics (traits of community, brilliance, and agency), and the professional role of an engineer, differ by children's gender or socio-economic status.

Participants included 500 Irish primary school children aged 10-12 years. This included approximately equal proportions of males and females; and students from DEIS/non-DEIS schools, i.e., lower/higher socioeconomic disadvantage. Participants completed a

classroom-based worksheet which included the Draw an Engineer Test, standardised measures and novel measures designed for this study: the Engineer Trait Perception Task whereby participants selected the traits they associated with engineers, e.g., brilliance; the Engineering Gender and Ethnicity Stereotypes Task whereby participants chose who they believed to be an engineer from a selection of diverse images; and an Engineer Occupation Task whereby participants selected which settings they believed engineers work.

All data have been collected, and analysis is in progress (pre-registration: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8FB3J>). No studies on children's perceptions of engineers investigate both physical and target characteristics, and there are no current quantitative tools to measure children's understanding of the professional role of engineering. These findings will establish how children in Ireland think about engineers and inform the design of an intervention to improve perceptions of engineering, and ultimately increase diversity in engineering.

Keywords: Engineering; Stereotypes; Primary School Children

Paper 2: Does a co-delivered teacher and engineer outreach programme (JEDI) reduce negative engineering stereotypes in primary school children?

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Abstract

Access to engineering education is disproportionate among groups with lower (e.g., women, rural dwellers, lower socioeconomic status) and higher social advantage (Engineers Ireland, 2025; Archer et al., 2015). Additionally, in Ireland children have limited exposure to engineering during their primary years schooling. In combination, these factors reduce the number, and diversity of children who follow engineering pathways. In this study it is argued that to address this disparity, an inclusive, multi-stakeholder model for engineering outreach is necessary at the primary school level.

The JEDI programme is a structured primary school engineering programme for 5th and 6th class children. It is designed to improve children's engineering skills and understanding of the attributes needed to be an engineer, and to address negative

stereotypes of engineers and engineering. JEDI is completed at a classroom level, and includes three teacher-led engineering sessions, and one session facilitated by a practicing engineer. During these sessions, children engage with the engineering design process, build prototypes, and use skills such as problem solving, creativity, and spatial reasoning.

In this study we evaluate the JEDI programme. Using a quasi-experimental controlled design, we compare the outcomes of children who participated in JEDI (n = 719) compared to those from a business-as-usual waiting control group (n=771). Participants completed pre-and post-evaluation workbooks. Data collection is complete and analysis is pending.

We anticipate that participation in JEDI will improve children's perceptions of engineers' physical and target characteristics, perceptions of the occupation of engineering, self-efficacy and interest in engineering. We anticipate these gains will be larger in DEIS schools. Findings will determine the effectiveness of JEDI in broadening engineering perceptions and reducing negative stereotypes, thereby supporting children's future engineering career path decisions. Moreover, the study introduces a measurement-to-intervention model promoting inclusive engineering engagement and education aligned with national STEM participation goals.

Keywords: Junior Engineer Development Initiative, Intervention, Primary School Engineering Outreach

Paper 3: Does teachers' participation in the JEDI programme change their perceptions of engineers/engineering or their self-efficacy in delivering engineering education?

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Abstract

Education systems around the world are adapting to ensure that children receive adequate training in all aspects of STEM, e.g., engineering learning goals have been introduced into the primary school curriculum in Ireland for the first time. Teachers play a central

role in implementing curriculum changes into classrooms. However, prior research shows that teachers hold misconceptions about engineering and engineers and report low levels of engineering teaching self-efficacy. This study investigates the impact of the Junior Engineer Development Initiative (JEDI), a novel, structured primary school engineering programme, as a tool for improving teachers' perceptions of engineering and engineers and their engineering teaching self-efficacy.

The overall goal of JEDI is to broaden participation in engineering and actively counter occupational stereotypes in 5th and 6th class children. The JEDI programme is co-delivered by teachers and engineers through four classroom-based sessions, with all stakeholders receiving professional development prior to the sessions. Data collection is in progress until April 2026. We estimate that participants will include 35 primary-level teachers (82% female; 55% from DEIS schools). The proposed data analysis has been pre-registered (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/74SGB>). A mixed-methods triangulation approach will be employed, combining quantitative analysis of pre- and post-intervention teacher evaluations adapted from validated perception scales, self-efficacy scales, and the Draw an Engineer Test, with qualitative analysis of post-intervention focus groups.

We anticipate participation in JEDI will improve teachers' perceptions of engineering and engineers and their engineering teaching self-efficacy, and expect that changes may be greater in female teachers. Findings will inform future iterations of the JEDI programme, and indeed any other primary school initiatives that include co-delivery. Optimising the effectiveness of engineering training in the classroom through improving teachers' perceptions and self-efficacy is essential as it may ultimately shift children's engineering perceptions and increase later STEM study.

Keywords: Teacher perceptions, Engineering stereotypes, Junior Engineer Development Initiative

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Leveraging Community Strengths to Support Place-Based Learning and Increase STEM Participation

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Abstract

Addressing the growing need for workers with Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) skills, to contribute to local economies and solutions for global challenges, requires innovative thinking and practical supports. In Tasmania - where this research was conducted - critical metal production faces significant workforce pressures. These pressures intersect with socio-economic challenges and low educational participation rates in the regional communities where the mines operate. Leveraging community strengths can advantage STEM learning in regional and rural schools to build understanding of local STEM industries and practices (Murphy et al., 2025).

This qualitative research project used an exploratory design to identify local strengths and assets that could support the development of STEM capital (Moote et al., 2020) with the goal of increasing interest and participation in mining and other STEM industries. The research question was: How might Tasmanian Regional Mining Communities capitalise on their strengths to build STEM capital and increase STEM career uptake? Twenty five nominated community, education and industry representatives generated data via the Lightning Decision Jam (LDJ) process (AJ&Smart, 2024), a novel outcome-focused approach. Transcribed recordings of the sessions were analysed thematically to support written strengths, challenges and potential solutions generated during LDJ.

Identified strengths included practices, structures and industries that incorporate historical, environmental and tourism assets; partnerships between schools and local industries; the knowledge of industry professionals; and programs supporting both adult learning and parents' engagement with education. The descriptions of successful programs generated during focus groups provide models for further partnerships to build community STEM Capital and personal STEM identities. The outcomes of this process have the potential to increase participation in STEM education and local STEM industries. Adaptation of both the process to identify strengths and the locally successful programs could support STEM industry participation in other communities.

Keywords: Community consultation, Industry partnerships, STEM Capital

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Co-Designing VR Chemistry Labs for Post-primary Education in Ireland

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Abstract

Experiential learning is essential for practical chemistry laboratory work (Van Dinther et al., 2023), yet post-primary schools are increasingly constrained by cost, infrastructure, and safety requirements (Atabek, 2019). This study examines whether Virtual Reality (VR) can provide laboratory learning opportunities that are difficult to implement in everyday school practice. We report on a 25-month study involving 164 stakeholders, including students, teachers, school leaders, parents, subject experts, and practitioners, guided by an Educational Design Research (EDR) (McKenney & Reeves, 2021) approach. The study is further informed by Experiential Learning Theory and the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, providing a lens to examine both student learning processes and teacher integration of VR. Phase One identified pedagogical and deployment requirements through a systematic literature review, a teacher survey, and semi-structured interviews. Phase Two involved an iterative design process in which three VR prototypes were developed and tested with users, incorporating feedback through cycles of evaluation and refinement. Phase Three evaluated the final VR application in post-primary classrooms with students and their teachers, using a mixed-methods approach including pre- and post-assessments, classroom observations, and participant feedback. Findings indicate significant gains in chemistry knowledge and procedural skills, alongside the development of transferable competencies such as autonomy, critical thinking, and confidence. The study also examines how VR reshapes classroom interactions and supports teachers in integrating technology into their practice. This research contributes to technology-enhanced science

education by demonstrating how an EDR approach can support the design and implementation of immersive learning tools. It offers both empirical evidence and practical insights to inform the integration of VR in real-world educational contexts.

Keywords: Participatory Design, Virtual Reality in Education, Chemistry Education, Post-Primary Education

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Using Virtual Reality to Bridge Disciplinary Knowledge Gaps in Pre-Service Junior Cycle Science Teachers in Ireland

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Abstract

Pre-service science teachers (PSTs) preparing to teach Junior Cycle Science in Ireland are expected to deliver content across multiple disciplinary strands, including Nature of Science, Earth and Space, Physics, Biology, and Chemistry. However, PSTs often enter teacher education programmes with uneven disciplinary backgrounds, leading to gaps in subject knowledge and reduced confidence when teaching outside their specialisation (Mizzi, 2013). This mismatch presents an ongoing challenge for initial teacher education and may impact instructional quality, teacher self-efficacy, and student learning (The Science Teaching Survey, 2023). This study investigates the potential of Virtual Reality (VR) to support PSTs in addressing these knowledge gaps. A sequential mixed-methods design is employed. Phase one involves a survey of 11 PSTs examining perceived subject knowledge, teaching self-efficacy, cognitive load, and attitudes toward cross-disciplinary teaching. Findings indicate that PSTs did not initially view VR as a suitable tool for supporting subject knowledge development. Phase two evaluates an existing immersive

VR titration application with 15 PSTs, focusing on a key chemistry concept. Pre- and post-intervention measures assess perceived competence, conceptual understanding, confidence in teaching the topic, and cognitive load, alongside focus groups exploring PSTs' experiences. Findings indicate that PSTs reported improved understanding of the titration process and its underlying concepts, as well as increased confidence in teaching the topic, including those with prior chemistry backgrounds. PSTs also identified VR as a valuable resource for lesson preparation and as a supportive tool across science disciplines. This study contributes to research on technology-enhanced teacher education by evaluating a specific VR application and demonstrating its potential to shift PSTs' perceptions of VR from a supplementary tool to a meaningful support for conceptual understanding and pedagogical confidence. The findings have implications for curriculum design, equitable teacher preparation, and the integration of immersive technologies in initial teacher education.

Keywords: Virtual Reality (VR), Pre-service Science Teachers, Teacher Education, Disciplinary Knowledge Gaps, Junior Cycle Science.

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Spatial Ability and Scientific Reasoning as Predictors of Performance on Motion Graphs Among Junior Cycle Science Students

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Abstract

The ability to think spatially, reason scientifically, and interpret abstract representations, are embedded within STEM education. Spatial ability is now recognised as a key aspect of a student's likelihood to succeed in STEM disciplines and is associated with high-performing students (Wai et al., 2009). Spatial ability has been shown to underpin a student's success in the study of engineering (Sorby et al., 2013), physics (Kozhevnikov et al., 2007), chemistry and beyond. Students often have difficulties when it comes to understanding and interpreting fundamental motion concepts. This study builds on

previous work, to investigate how spatial ability and scientific reasoning contribute to performance on motion graphing tasks. This study was conducted in six second level schools in Ireland. Tests of spatial ability, scientific reasoning, and kinematics graph interpretation were administered across 1-4th year during Junior Cycle / Transition year science classes.

The relationship between these variables was investigated. The sample size was n=472. A dimension of scientific reasoning, proportional reasoning, emerged as a unique predictor of performance on motion graphing tasks, with scientific reasoning fully mediating the relationship between spatial ability and performance on motion graphs. Scientific reasoning was measured by the Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning, which places students into three different reasoning levels based on test score: Concrete, Transitional, and Formal. Over 50% of the sample were still found in the Concrete reasoning stage by the time they reached Transition year. Scientific reasoning answer patterns were also analysed and compared to spatial ability and motion graph interpretation. A novel activity was developed and piloted to further explore students' understanding of motion graphs. Findings revealed a significant relationship between scientific reasoning and performance on position-time and velocity-time graphs. In contrast, spatial ability was found to be significantly associated with performance on acceleration-time graphs

Keywords: Spatial Ability, Scientific Reasoning, Motion Graphs

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Contextualisation in educational research: a case study demonstrating the relationship between a study's motivation, the featured data and the analysis method

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Abstract

This poster presentation explores the data analysis tools that we use and the decisions that guide their use, highlighting how research context should inform methodological choices. Although this presentation, drawing on Howard et al. (2026), centres on cluster analysis in educational contexts, the broader principle of contextualisation applies across research studies more generally.

Cluster analysis groups observations so that those within the same cluster are more similar to each other than to those in other clusters e.g., grouping students who exhibit similar attendance behaviours. There are several different cluster analysis methods, and each method could produce a different grouping of observations. Researchers often choose a cluster analysis method based on their type of data and/or previous studies which they perceive to be similar to their own study. This may result in overlooking a clustering method that is better aligned with their study's context.

We demonstrate contextualisation in cluster analysis by using the Open University Learning Analytics dataset (OULAD) and the motivation of identifying students who are at-risk of failing or dropping out early in a module. We discuss the educational context behind this motivation, describe which data from the OULAD might best align to this motivation, and discuss how an appropriate clustering method may be selected based on this motivation. We show the solution for two clustering methods, k-means and model-based clustering. While both clustering solutions are valid, we discuss how the model-based clustering solution may be the preferred clustering solution owing to the educational context of identifying at-risk students e.g., when planning a targeted intervention, considerations are cluster size and uncertainty in cluster membership allocation.

In summary, we argue that the most successful studies are those where the research question inform the data (analysis) decisions. In addition, we comment on how the concept of contextualisation can be taught to students.

Keywords: Contextualisation, Data Analysis, Higher Education Practice

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Unlearning Modernity: Remaking Science Education in the Anthropocene

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Abstract

Across the disciplines, contemporary science is reorienting itself toward relationality, uncertainty, and intelligences beyond the human — from the distributed cognition of slime moulds and the communicative agency of plants to the entangled knowledge production of holobiont biology or quantum mechanics (Barad, 2007). In cases from animal-technology collaboration to anti-colonial research practices (Liboiron, 2021), the sciences are coming to terms with a world that is entangled, co-constituted, and not fully knowable from a detached vantage point. Yet, science education, even when positioned as a response to the challenges of the Anthropocene — climate breakdown, biodiversity collapse, resource depletion and deepening social inequalities — remains anchored in the modernist logics of control, separability, technological determinism and human exceptionalism that have exacerbated the polycrisis. This misalignment is not incidental but structural, rooted in science education's inheritance of a modernist framework that emerging science itself is abandoning (Vossoughi, Marin & Bang, 2023). Drawing on developments across the natural and social sciences, we suggest that science education has a responsibility to follow to directions being taken by emerging science. We propose that collectively unlearning the habits and mindsets that are no longer fit for purpose is not a retreat from rigour in science education, but a precondition for it. This challenges the dominant model of science education as a pipeline from disciplinary knowledge to technological progress to economic growth, and establishes the case for a fundamental reorientation: from training problem-solvers to cultivating participants in knowledge generation, world-building, and the shared stewardship of planetary futures.

Keywords: Planetary Health & Action, Anthropocene, Science–society relations

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Authentic Datasets in Secondary Science: A Systematic Review of Classroom Integration and Impacts

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Abstract

This literature review examines how big data, defined here as authentic, large, or complex real-world datasets, is being integrated into secondary science classrooms, and with what reported effects on students' learning, engagement, and equity. We first situate the review within contemporary calls to engage students in core scientific practices, posing questions, analysing and interpreting evidence, and constructing explanations through authentic datasets (Arnold et al., 2022), while acknowledging teachers' concern that such work, though pedagogically promising, can be practically burdensome without targeted, inquiry-aligned supports. The review then considers the argument that task structures not data portals alone are pivotal for making complex data pedagogically tractable (Salimpour et al., 2021), and that researcher teacher partnerships can improve classroom readiness (Park & Yoon, 2024).

Against this backdrop, we conduct a systematic review of peer-reviewed empirical studies at the secondary school level across ERIC, Scopus and Web of Science. We extract and synthesise data on dataset provenance and complexity; curricular contexts and disciplinary aims; inquiry-aligned task structures (e.g., question formulation, data analysis/interpretation, evidence-based explanation); tools and scaffolds; teacher professional learning and supports; and reported outcomes (conceptual understanding, data literacy, engagement, equity). Our analysis intends to characterise the landscape with thematic synthesis to identify pedagogical approaches, reported affordances and constraints.

The review addresses the primary question: To what extent do peer-reviewed studies integrate authentic, large, or complex datasets into secondary classrooms, and what impacts do these approaches have on students' learning (conceptual understanding and data literacy), engagement, and equity? As findings are not yet known, the paper outlines anticipated contributions: (a) a field map of integration approaches and contexts; (b) a synthesis of outcome evidence and measurement approaches; and (c) emergent design principles, aligned with inquiry-centred scaffolds and partnership models, intended to lower practical barriers for teachers and inform initial teacher education.

Keywords: authentic datasets; big data; secondary/post-primary science

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Design-based Learning for Improved Spatial Skills, Creativity, and Performance in STEM.

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Abstract

Spatial ability is long considered a key component of intelligence and a strong predictor of STEM achievement (Wai et al., 2009). Research into spatial cognition reveals its vital role in creative problem-solving (Kell et al., 2013) with evidence to suggest a reciprocal relationship between spatial skills and hands-on STEM experiences (Julià & Antolí, 2016). Key aims of the new Irish primary STEM curriculum are centred around supporting and fostering the development of critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving through cross-disciplinary STEM experiences. This study explored the role of design-based learning in the development of spatial skills in a STEM context providing insights into how design-based learning can connect multiple domains that bridge Art and STEM (STEAM).

A design-based learning intervention was developed aimed at engaging pupils, aged 10 to 13 years old, in creative ideation, sketching, hands-on prototyping, and mechanical problem-solving. The impact of the intervention was examined using a mixed methods design with quantitative pre and post-test measures to assess the changes in spatial reasoning and creative drawing ability. The qualitative aspect of the study examined multimodal data in the form of children's sketches, diagrammatic drawings and audiovisual recordings aimed at capturing moment-to-moment emergence of spatial communication (e.g., gesture, language, and object manipulation) during the design activity.

Overall, the preliminary results indicate that a spatially demanding design-based learning activity has the potential to enhance creativity and spatial skills in primary school aged children with particular gains for girls. Practically, the findings seek to inform the primary curriculum developers and teachers of a pedagogically sound, integrated design-based learning activity that fosters creativity and spatial skills for long-term success in STEM.

Keywords: Keywords: Desing-based learning, STEM, Spatial Abilities

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A thematic analysis of teachers' experiences of professional development to teach spatial ability

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Abstract

Spatial ability is an important component of secondary school teaching programmes, as it can help students develop stronger conceptualizations and mental representations of STEM topics, improve their academic achievement in STEM, and encourage them to pursue careers in related fields. Research suggests that spatial ability can be developed through practice, leading to improved learning outcomes in STEM. However, few studies have investigated teachers' perspectives on professional development (PD) for teaching spatial ability and the importance of spatial ability in secondary school teaching.

This study aimed to explore teachers' perspectives and experiences of a PD programme that trained teachers to implement the Developing Spatial Thinking course (Sorby & Baartmans, 2000) for transition year (TY) students. This study focuses specifically on identifying teachers' experiences of the training, with particular attention to their affective responses, confidence, and engagement with spatial ability instruction.

A total of 121 teachers participated in the PD programme over five academic years, from 2021 to 2025. From this group, forty-one teachers participated in focus groups, and eight took part in individual semi-structured interviews. The interview and focus group data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (RTA), following the guidelines of Braun and Clarke (2012, 2019, 2021).

The interview data indicate that, even though teachers valued the PD training structure and supporting resources (videos, software, manipulatives), many remained apprehensive about teaching the course for the first time. The most surprising finding is that, despite these challenges and concerns about the implementation of the course in practice, teachers demonstrated a strong willingness to explore additional activities for developing spatial ability in mathematics teaching. One important finding was that teachers highlighted the crucial role of spatial ability for mathematics teaching, but noted that, without PD training and practical sessions, even experienced teachers may find the tasks challenging to teach.

Keywords: STEM education, spatial ability, teacher professional development

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Young Children's Conceptions of Luck and Its Influence on Their Probabilistic Judgements

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Abstract

In our everyday lives, we hear mention of luck in a variety of contexts. Many people believe themselves or others to be particularly lucky or unlucky and we may have our own special 'lucky numbers', believed to influence the chance of our success at a particular task. Luck is often used as an explanation for unusual or unexpected events (Woolley & Kelley, 2020). While it has been well-established that luck frequently

impacts the probabilistic judgments of adults (e.g., Darke & Freedman, 1997), limited research has been conducted to explore this phenomenon in children.

In this study, data were collected through individual task-based interviews with 72 children aged four to eight years. The children engaged with a range of probabilistic tasks relating to the constructs of probability of an event, probability comparisons, and sample space. Analysis revealed two distinct categories of responses pertaining to how the participating children viewed luck: some children understood luck to be something that causes events to happen in their lives while others viewed luck as something that can be possessed. An analysis of the frequency of the children's references to luck across the interviews revealed that despite the influence of luck on adults' capacity to think rationally, the participating children focused largely on quantitative factors such as the proportion of each possible outcome in the sample space. This suggests that young children may possess a latent capacity for rational probabilistic thinking that is not always overridden by heuristics such as luck. However, contextual factors such as task attributes and the nature of the tools used may also have influenced the children's reliance on quantitative judgements.

In this presentation, I share examples of the children's comments to explore the two distinct categories of thinking in relation to luck. I discuss how the design of the tasks may have facilitated a more quantitative focus than is typically observed in adult populations. I conclude by arguing that the relationship between task context and luck-based reasoning requires further exploration to better understand how to support robust probabilistic foundations in early mathematics education.

Keywords: Probabilistic thinking; Luck; Task-based interviews

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Examining the competence and confidence of physics teachers

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Abstract

When preparing future physics teachers, a key goal of educational programmes is supporting students to become competent and confident teachers. Competence in physics teaching includes teachers developing strong physics knowledge, complemented with an understanding of how to teach this content effectively. The concept of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) (Shulman, 1986) therefore should be the essential part of the preparation of physics teachers. However, the PCK itself is not sufficient to become an efficient teacher. A physics teachers must build their confidence for teaching and develop a strong self-efficacy about their role as a teachers and influence on student learning. Although both confidence and self-efficacy may seem similar, the difference is visible in the action (Bandura, 1997). Confident and self-efficacious teacher should be aware of the teaching process and able to learn and improve the teaching practice. Several studies report on pre-service and in-service physics teachers' self-efficacy for learning and teaching physics (McLoughlin et al., 2024), (Gammell et al., 2024). These, as well as other studies focus on the measuring of the self-efficacy and often points out the gender difference.

This leads to an important question: What are key stakeholders in physics teacher education, namely, pre-service teachers, in-service teachers, and teacher educators, understanding of physics teacher competence and confidence? Semi-structured interviews were conducted with ten individuals, representatives of each group, to gain a deeper understanding of differences in perspectives. Their insights provide valuable insights into different definitions and perceptions and their interpretation of what is meant by competence, the role of self-efficacy on teacher's beliefs and practices, and experiences/factors that influence the development of a teacher confidence. This study will discuss differences in understanding of these concepts between participant groups and highlight changes in perception among participants.

Keywords: physics teacher, competence, confidence

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Culturally Responsive Engineering Design Process (CREDP) for Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education Equity: A Comparative Literature Review of Ireland and Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

Equitable STEM education represents a critical policy imperative internationally, including Ireland and Tamil Nadu State, India which is the focus of this study. In Ireland, the non-DEIS schools have higher uptake than DEIS schools in every key STEM area. Ireland's STEM Education Policy Statement 2017-2026 prioritises teacher capacity building and equitable learner engagement (Department of Education and Science, 2017). In India, students from minority background and students from tribal background comprise lower percentage points of STEM enrolment compared to their general peers. Tamil Nadu's State Education Policy (2024) emphasises STEAM education and equitable, socially just education (Government of Tamil Nadu, 2024). This Conference presentation will outline the literature review on culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) fostering equity and diversity in STEM education, for this emerging qualitative comparative case study between a primary school(class 5) in Tamil Nadu, India and Limerick, Ireland. This comparison will also build inclusive understanding of CRP and design-based STEM pedagogy - learning beyond Eurocentric models.

Based on the policy analysis and literature review, the findings indicate that both countries' policies prioritise equity yet reveal stark disparities in STEM participation, achievement and access across marginalised students. Ireland shows DEIS students score less in Science and Math and face subject-choice gaps, while India expands higher education yet faces low school achievement and regional inequalities. From the findings, Ladson-Billings, G. (1995b) CRP emerge as a tool for operationalising equity commitments and academic achievements in STEM learning for marginalised students through Culturally Responsive Engineering Design Process (CREDP) (Manuel et al., 2023). Research demonstrates that culturally responsive engineering design teaching leads to improved learning outcomes particularly for marginalised students. Globally, teachers value culturally responsive STEM pedagogies but face systemic preparation barriers. Unaddressed deficit beliefs among teachers about marginalised students'

capacity remain persistent barriers to meaningful STEM participation both in India and Ireland.

Keywords: Equity in STEM, Culturally Responsive Pedagogy, Engineering Design Process

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Doodle STEAM: Fostering Knowledge and Skills with Families Across the Lifespan

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Abstract

Literature has indicated that research on early Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Maths (STEAM) interventions for parents is limited (McNally et al., 2022), despite the importance of parental input in supporting young children's STEAM learning. In response, we developed Doodle STEAM; an evidence-informed programme for parents of children aged 6-8 years. Delivered in schools, the programme aims to develop parental confidence in promoting and engaging in STEAM activities with their children in the home. Early parental support provides a strong basis for their children's engagement in STEAM subjects. This parental involvement is important for developing positive attitudes and early skills for children's success in school, engagement and learning. Parental involvement is cited as central in the curriculum frameworks for the early years and primary education ((National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2009, 2023). The programme is facilitated by Home School Community Liaisons, and is implemented over an 8-week period. Each week focuses on a different STEAM topic, and involves fun hands-on activities which can be replicated at home. Although primarily aimed at parents, children are welcomed to get involved in the sessions, spending time with their parents on exploratory activities. In 2025, 367 parents and 367 children, across 28 schools engaged with Doodle STEAM, and 42 Doodle STEAM facilitators were trained across Ireland.

The evaluation was conducted using a mixed-methods approach, guided by an agreed framework and ethical approval, incorporating parent/carer surveys and focus groups with participating primary school children, their parents who participated alongside them, and HSCLs who facilitated the programme, with pre and post quantitative data compared using descriptive methods, and qualitative data summarised and subjected to content analysis which supports the assertion that Doodle STEAM enhances parental confidence . Findings (Haran, 2024) and competence in engaging in STEAM activities, and that the programme supports children's STEAM development and (Butler, 2025). Plans for future expansion of Doodle STEAM, to early years provision, and older children will be discussed.

Keywords: Parental Engagement; STEAM

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‘Let’s Sail off the Island’: Educator Agency and Integrated STEAM in Early Childhood

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Abstract

Aistear, the Early Childhood Curriculum Framework (NCCA, 2024) requires that young children, ‘Engage, explore and experiment in their environment through integrated artistic, linguistic, musical, geographical, historical and STEM learning experiences’ (p.29). However, Irish early childhood educators (ECEs) often lack the knowledge, skills and confidence necessary to support young children's developing STEM knowledge and inquiry (O'Neill et al., 2023). Government reports acknowledge that STEM education in preschool settings is less well developed than in other educational sectors (DES, 2020).

This presentation reports on one strand of the ERASMUS+ funded OUTSTE(A)M project (2024–2026), an initiative designed to support educators of children aged 3–8 in implementing integrated, outdoor STEAM learning. Drawing on the implementation of the learning scenario *Let's Sail off the Island*, we examine how one Irish preschool adapted this structured STEAM scenario to suit their specific context and the developmental profiles of the children in the setting.

The scenario invited children to solve a narrative problem—helping a stranded marine biologist escape from an island—through inquiry into weight, capacity, floating and sinking, culminating in the design of boats. While the learning design foregrounded inquiry-based, interdisciplinary STEAM, the key finding from this case was the centrality of educator agency. Educators critically assessed the scenario, re-sequenced elements, extended play episodes, and embedded intentional teaching moments to scaffold conceptual understanding.

This case demonstrates that high-quality early STEAM learning depends not on scripted materials but on the agentic educator who can integrate play-based pedagogy with purposeful instruction and adapt curriculum responsively. We conclude by reflecting on educator perceptions of the process and implications for early years policy, professional learning, and the development of adaptable STEAM resources that position educators as curriculum decision-makers rather than implementers.

Key words: STEAM education; Agentic educator; Play-Based Learning

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Innovative Pedagogies for Social Justice: Integrating Empathy, STEM, and Entrepreneurial Thinking in the EMPOWER Outreach Programme

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Abstract

Preparing young people to navigate societal, environmental and technological challenges of the 21st century requires STEM education approaches that are interdisciplinary, learner centred and grounded in authentic real-world engagement. This paper presents findings from *EMPOWER*, a week-long entrepreneurial community-based STEM outreach programme for students aged 14–17, which integrates innovative pedagogies encompassing empathy, and human centred design as core pedagogical drivers. Developed by a multidisciplinary team of STEM educators, community engagement specialists, engineers and entrepreneurship practitioners, EMPOWER positions STEM not only as a disciplinary endeavour, but as a platform for active citizenship, critical inquiry and societal problem solving. Building on research in socio-scientific issue-based STEM learning (Zeidler et al., 2005; Sadler, 2011), human-centred design education (Brown, 2008; Carroll et al., 2014) and maker-oriented pedagogies (Halverson & Sheridan, 2014), EMPOWER adopts an interdisciplinary, community-engaged approach to STEM learning.

Through a sequence of maker-based workshops, including socio-scientific investigations, design sprints, engineering design challenges, empathy building exercises and interdisciplinary creative tasks, participants engage with real world problems such as homelessness, mental health and wellbeing, food poverty, climate action, and equitable access to education.

Data from participants demonstrate significant growth in teamwork, creativity, empathy, problem identification skills, and confidence in tackling meaningful issues through STEM. Participants reported increased awareness of societal challenges, deeper understanding of human-centred design and strengthened motivation to engage in community and environmentally focused innovation.

As a community-based intervention, EMPOWER also faces challenges related to its short-duration format, reliance on facilitation expertise and constraints in assessing longer-term impact.

The findings highlight EMPOWER as a novel pedagogical model that integrates STEM, human-centred innovation and entrepreneurial thinking to foster agency, empathy and interdisciplinary problem-solving contributing to research advocating for STEM education that is contextualised, learner driven, and socially transformative, supporting a

STEM literate generation equipped to navigate complexity and co-create more equitable futures.

Keywords: Social Justice; STEM education; Entrepreneurship education; Innovative pedagogies; Human-centred design

Gender Issues: Assessment Design, Confidence, and Access in High-Stakes Mathematics Education

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Abstract

High-stakes mathematics assessments play a pivotal role in shaping students' educational trajectories, self-belief, and access to STEM careers. The introduction of a revised mathematics curriculum in Ireland ("Project Maths") significantly impacted the state Leaving Certificate examinations from 2012 onwards. A persistent gender gap favouring boys has emerged at the highest grade levels of the Higher course, despite broadly equal participation rates.

The aim of this research is to explore potential contributors to this divergence beyond differences in mathematical ability, with particular attention to assessment design, access to curriculum experiences, and student confidence. The research is informed by established findings regarding self-efficacy and equity in mathematics education (Breda et al., 2020; O'Rourke & Prendergast, 2021; Lindner et al., 2022). Using a controlled, in-school experimental design across 22 diverse schools, students (n = 329) were given a "mock" examination that mirrored the structure and marking scheme of the state examination. Survey data on subject access, subject choice, and self-perceived confidence were collected alongside performance data. Descriptive and comparative analyses were used to examine patterns across gender and examination component.

While boys and girls reported comparable mathematical achievement at Junior Cycle, pronounced differences by gender emerged on the "Contexts and Applications" component of the "mock" examination, which emphasises unseen problem-solving. Reported confidence showed the same pattern, with the gap most pronounced for "Contexts and Applications"; girls also reported lower enjoyment and lower confidence in spatial reasoning. Notably, girls were less likely to have access to Applied Mathematics - a subject linked with higher grades in Mathematics and less likely to choose it where available.

This research contributes to international discussions on inclusion in STEM and highlights how assessment design and curricular access - rather than student attributes - may shape STEM participation, with implications for workforce diversity and societal capacity in STEM.

Keywords: Mathematics gender gap, Assessment Design, Mathematics self-efficacy

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Checking for Understanding or Supporting New Learning? Teachers' Use of Retrieval-Based Methodologies in Mathematics

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Abstract

Research has consistently shown that effective mathematics learning depends on making connections with prior knowledge, with retrieval practice frequently promoted as a means of enhancing the learning of new, related material (May, 2021). However, evidence on retrieval practice remains largely confined to laboratory research, with limited understanding of how, why, or even whether it is enacted in post-primary mathematics classrooms (Pan et al., 2024). Therefore, teachers may be encouraged to adopt retrieval-based approaches without a picture of their pedagogical purposes or alignment with classroom practice. Unlike prior studies, this research questions: How do Irish post-primary mathematics teachers use and perceive retrieval-based activities?

To address this gap, this study reports findings from a national survey of a large sample of post-primary mathematics teachers conducted in January 2026. It offers a systematic examination of teachers' current practice with particular attention to the purposes and priorities underpinning their use of retrieval-based activities, rather than frequency alone. Item formats included opinions on classroom-based scenarios, Likert-type statements and open-ended questions. Quantitative data underwent descriptive and inferential analysis

using SPSS and qualitative data were analysed using an inductive thematic analysis approach guided by Braun and Clarke (2022).

These findings contribute to research in mathematics education and cognitive science by identifying a clear gap between the theorised benefits of retrieval practice and its enacted purposes in Irish post-primary mathematics classrooms. While participants consistently valued the role of prior knowledge in supporting new learning, classroom practice prioritised checking for understanding over deliberately using retrieval to support the teaching of new concepts. Building on this national picture, the study highlights the need for classroom-based interventions that examine how retrieval practice can be designed, enacted and experienced by both teachers and students.

Keywords: Retrieval practice, Mathematics education, Prior knowledge activation

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Explore, Explain, Expand - a lesson design Framework for Pre-Service STEM teachers.

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Abstract

Teaching is multifaceted and highly conceptual. Lesson planning is often used as an approach to introduce novice pre-service teachers (PSTs) to effective teaching. The use of generic lesson templates which follow linear models have been common practice. These are often used in an effort to simplify the complexities of teaching to steps and routines^{1,2}. It is our experience that this can lead to rigid lesson designs that do not address classroom dynamics and student needs. These lessons often focus on covering content instead of teaching for understanding and are more focused on the role of the PST than student learning.

Recognising these challenges, we designed a framework that supports PSTs in designing and teaching Science and Mathematics lessons. The Explore, Explain, Expand (3E)

framework is derived from a theoretical framework Dewey³ uses for thinking grounded in student learning. It includes an inductive exploration phase that builds on prior learning and scaffolding towards the central concept, an explain phase where the teacher frames the initial explorations into a cohesive concept, using correct terminology, and an expand phase which allows students to apply the concept in new situations. A key aspect of this approach is to provide model-based lessons where PSTs experience and reflect on lesson design.

This approach was implemented with PSTs (n=83) in the first and second years of the undergraduate programmes. We tracked how this approach supported them to design and teach lessons that are focused on student learning and development of conceptual understanding.

Data collected includes PSTs microteaching videos and design rationales/reflections. A thematic analysis indicates that the 3E Framework provides PSTs with opportunities to better enhance their own conceptual understanding as well as to make a transformational shift between teachers as disseminators of knowledge to teachers who support construction of understanding.

Keywords: Lesson Design, Teacher Education, Teacher Perceptions

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It's that Plane: Theoretical Perspectives informing Effective Teaching of Spatial Reasoning in Geometry

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Abstract

In recent years, research in geometry education has expanded, offering a range of theoretical perspectives that focus on specific geometric processes and elements (Azarello, Olivero, Paola, and Robutti, 2002). These perspectives highlight the complexity of geometry teaching and learning and emphasise the importance of theoretically grounded approaches to instruction. Geometry is a key strand of the Irish mathematics curriculum at both Junior and Senior Cycle levels. However, despite its

importance, many students and mathematics teachers demonstrate limited understanding of geometry. In addition, avoidance of geometry teaching and negative learning experiences have contributed to ongoing challenges in geometry education in recent years (Chang and Engelhard Jr, 2016). The overall aim of this research is to investigate whether the design, implementation, and evaluation of a Transition Year geometry intervention can influence post-primary mathematics teachers' perspectives and self-efficacy in teaching spatial reasoning through geometry. In particular, the study explores how such an intervention may support teachers in developing greater self-efficacy and positively influence their teaching experiences and perspectives regarding spatial reasoning and geometry instruction. This poster presents the theoretical framework that will inform the future design of the intervention. At the time of this study, Phase 1 data collection has been completed, and analysis of these findings will directly inform the subsequent development of the intervention. Therefore, the intervention itself has not yet been designed; instead, this work focuses on synthesising the findings from Phase 1 with established theoretical perspectives to guide its future construction. The theoretical framework integrates three key perspectives: spatial reasoning (Maier, 1996), geometry grounded in the Van Hiele model of geometric thinking (Crowley, 1987), and effective teaching practices based on established national guidance in geometry education (Department of Education and Skills; National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2015).

Keywords: Mathematics Education, Geometry, Spatial Reasoning, Self-efficacy

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Beyond the Algorithm: Reclaiming the Human Element in AI-Enhanced Science Communication

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Abstract

In an era of fast-moving information cycles, STEM literacy in the general population is critical, requiring the integration of technical skills with a strong social focus. This paper presents reflections from the design and implementation of a new postgraduate module, AI and Emerging Technologies, which examines how science communication skills can be developed in the context of AI while foregrounding human centred values.

The primary aim of this curriculum is to help learners use technology to re-imagine scientific stories and make complex concepts more understandable. Guided by a human-centred design approach (De Silva et al., 2024), the module promotes a model of AI literacy understood as a multidimensional capability that includes technical understanding alongside critical, ethical, and contextual awareness (O'Sullivan et al., 2025). Within this framework, human-centredness emphasises human agency and educational responsibility, ensuring that AI supports learning and communication rather than prioritising technical or algorithmic efficiency alone.

The methodology is grounded in the theoretical foundations of Bucchi and Trench (2025), who frame science communication as a social practice requiring critical dialogue. A central conceptual approach is the use of independent reflective practice, where students evaluate the evolving role of the human communicator within an AI-influenced landscape. Through this, students learn to critically assess how these digital ecosystems influence public understanding and trust in scientific institution. By treating AI as a partner for inquiry rather than a substitute for thought, this approach fosters the ability to identify algorithmic bias, misinformation, and the loss of authentic human connection.

Preliminary findings from student reflective practice suggest that this framework empowers learners to remain capable STEM advocates who can lead technological tools rather than follow them. It is expected that this performative, multidisciplinary approach provides a scalable model for other faculties to foster future skills while safeguarding the integrity of scientific information.

Keywords: science communication, Artificial Intelligence, digital literacy

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STEM Education in Practice: Designing Authentic and Gender-Responsive Informatics Learning with the THINKER Framework

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Abstract

Recent European policy reports indicate that STEM education across Europe continues to face persistent challenges in both computational competence development and gender participation gaps (European Commission, 2020). Despite sustained policy investment, informatics education often remains fragmented and insufficiently connected to authentic, real-world problem-solving contexts, contributing to the early disengagement of girls and other underrepresented groups.

The THINKER Erasmus+ project responds to this challenge through a pan-European, research-informed framework that supports teachers in designing inclusive and authentic informatics learning experiences. The framework is grounded in computational thinking, inquiry-based STEM education, and the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model—which conceptualises the integration of technology, pedagogy, and subject content in effective teaching (Mishra & Koehler, 2006)—as well as gender-responsive pedagogy.

This presentation focuses specifically on **how inclusive STEM design principles can be implemented and evaluated in classroom practice**. Drawing on data from over 100 pilot schools across multiple European countries, we present:

- Empirically identified barriers to participation in computing, particularly for girls
- Two classroom case studies demonstrating inclusive task design, including community-based computing challenges and collaborative inquiry activities designed to increase girls' participation and confidence in computing.
- Observed relationships between teacher practices (e.g., questioning strategies, group dynamics, assessment design) on student engagement and participation

We also outline the project's **evaluation approach**, which combines classroom observations, teacher feedback, and student participation data to assess changes in engagement, inclusivity, and computational thinking development. Findings indicate that aligning authentic problem contexts with inclusive pedagogical strategies and teacher

professional development can contribute to measurable improvements in participation and engagement in STEM learning.

- Participants will engage with selected classroom cases and leave with:
- A research-informed framework for inclusive STEM task design
- Practical examples of lesson adaptations
- Evidence-based strategies to support broader participation in computing

This session is relevant to educators, researchers, and policymakers seeking scalable, research-informed approaches to inclusive STEM education.

Keywords: STEM education; computational thinking; gender inclusion

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An investigation into first year undergraduate students' thoughts while engaging with procedural and problem-solving questions in mathematics

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Abstract

Like many other countries internationally, the second level (12-18 years) mathematics curriculum in Ireland changed from one where rote learning and procedural skills were the focus to a curriculum which placed an emphasis on deep conceptual understanding and problem-solving in real life contexts (Cunningham, Close & Shiel, 2016; Faulkner et al., 2021). Faulkner et al. (2021) developed a diagnostic test to examine and compare beginning undergraduate students' procedural and problem-solving skills after the introduction of these curriculum changes. This study found that incoming undergraduate students performed statistically lower on average when engaging with problem-solving questions when compared with their performance when engaging with procedural questions. The authors acknowledged that more longitudinal quantitative research, along

with a qualitative investigation, needed to be carried out to examine this difference in performance. This research aims to carry out such an investigation using the Faulkner et. al (2021) diagnostic test combined with a 'think-aloud' protocol. The 'think-aloud' protocol requires students to verbalise their thoughts while engaging with a given mathematical task, allowing one to access what is happening in the student's short-term memory (Cowan, 2019; Ericsson, 2003). This research paper outlines quantitative and qualitative data collected in TU Dublin over the academic years 2022/23, 2023/24 and 2024/25. The quantitative findings are in line with those found by Faulkner et. al (2021) while additional insights are revealed about the nature of students challenges via the think-aloud data, which focuses on interviews conducted during the 2023/24 and 2024/25 academic years. An initial analysis from these interviews suggests that students felt that the presence of additional text had a negative impact on their performance for the problem-solving questions in comparison to the procedural questions.

Keywords: procedural skills, problem-solving skills, think-aloud

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All STEAMed up about Herbaria: learning from preserved plant specimens

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Abstract

A herbarium is a collection of dried, pressed plants ranging from a small collection in schools of a few dozen specimens to an individually funded institution with millions of specimens (national herbaria). Regardless of the size, their primary purpose is the same: to be a learning resource about all forms of plants (and fungi, lichens, and heterokonts).

The idea of drying and pressing plants and fixing them to paper in order to use the resulting sheets to teach learners about plants, horticulture, and medicine appears in the European Renaissance as far as is known, and the earliest extant herbaria date from the mid-16th century. In time, universities were keen to adopt them in their botany or biology departments, and some became funded through endowments, and they became de rigueur in the teaching of biology per se until the mid-20th century. Recently, though, European or 'western' learners have become ever more oblivious to the whole branch of organic life termed 'plants', so much so that some authors named a phenomenon termed 'plant blindness' (Wandersee & Schussler, 1999, 2001) and latterly "plant awareness disparity" (Parsley, 2020) describes a common condition where humans are unable to identify plants in their own environment. A renewed awareness of the problem coincides with the current global anthropogenic biodiversity crisis (Naggs, 2017). The author asks the question: "Do herbaria have a role in the current readjustment concerning learning about plants through the lens of STEAM?" Surprisingly, Krosnick & Moore (2024) argue that herbarium specimens may inspire interest in plants even more effectively than living collections as a result of the unique historical, sociological, artistic, epigraphical, and geographical information they contain. Herbaria display metadata and interpolate with digital media in databases, photographic records, and global information systems.

Keywords: STEAM, Herbaria, Biodiversity Extinction

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Understanding Ireland's Performance in Measurement and Geometry: Insights from TIMSS 2023

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Abstract

Ireland has consistently performed strongly in international assessments of mathematics including the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and Progress for International Student Assessment (PISA). However, closer examination of the performance across mathematical content areas reveals persistent relative weaknesses have been identified in the areas of Measurement and Geometry (Shape and Space). These weaknesses have been identified in both international assessments and national assessments such as the National Assessment of Mathematics and English Reading (NAMER).

Ireland has consistently participated in TIMSS at Fourth Class (Grade) since 2011 and across all cycles of TIMSS since 2011, students in Ireland have performed significantly lower on the content area of Measurement and Geometry compared to mathematics achievement overall (Eivers & Clerkin, 2012; McHugh et al., 2024). National research and policy initiatives have similarly highlighted the need to strengthen students' skills in these areas, including research commissioned by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NicMhúirí, 2020), the National, Literacy, Numeracy, and Digital Literacy Strategy, and Department of Education Inspectorate Reports.

This study examines whether these relative weaknesses are consistent across the student population or concentrated among certain subgroups (e.g., by gender, socioeconomic status, school gender). Using data from TIMSS 2023, bivariate and multivariate analyses are conducted to investigate patterns of achievement in Measurement and Geometry relative to overall mathematics performance.

This research forms part of a broader PhD study that seeks to understand the underlying causes of these weaknesses and to inform improvements in teaching practices, teacher training, and curriculum design aimed at addressing them.

Keywords: Mathematics, Measurement & Geometry, TIMSS

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Influence of industry internship on teachers preparedness for designing STEM learning experiences

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Abstract

The rapid advances in technology and innovation to support people to live and thrive in a globally connected society requires an agile and resilient STEM workforce with appropriate knowledge and skills and STEM careers (Bong & Chen, 2024). Over the past twenty years, education systems have focussed on the development of STEM education curricula that supports students to integrate learning from across the STEM disciplines of science, technology, engineering and mathematics. The critical importance of preparing teachers for the development of appropriate knowledge and skills for designing STEM learning experiences has been highlighted (Hurley, Butler & McLoughlin, 2023) This study reports on the influence of a 12-week industry internship on primary and secondary teachers' preparedness for the STEM classroom. An overview of teacher's roles and experiences in industry will be presented along with feedback collected from 44 teachers through an online survey directly after they have completed their internship in September 2024. Teachers' responses to open response questions were independently coded and data analysis occurred in a combined inductive and deductive manner. This study will discuss findings in relation to teacher's understanding of STEM and the interconnections between STEM disciplines, and their confidence in designing STEM learning opportunities and promoting STEM careers with their students in the primary and secondary classrooms.

Keywords: Integrated STEM Education, Immersive learning experiences, STEM Teacher Education

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The Role of Teacher Noticing in Mathematics Classroom Discourse

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Abstract

Teacher noticing has become a prominent construct in research on teacher education in recent years. This qualitative, interpretive case study aims to investigate the noticing processes of a group of primary teachers conducting a lesson study cycle focused on promoting maths talk during the teaching of directed numbers in a fifth-class setting. Data will be collected through audio recording of the participants' lesson study meetings along with video recordings of the lessons taught. This study aims to incorporate Lee and Choy's (2019) teacher noticing framework with Sfard's (2008) commognitive theory, which views learning as changes in discourse and noticing as a discourse structure covering observation, interpretation and reasoning processes (van Es, 2011). The study aims to highlight teachers' noticing and explore how teachers' actions and instructional responses influence mathematics classroom talk. By positioning noticing itself as a discursive practice, this study advances a novel analytical lens that bridges cognitive and discursive perspectives in mathematics education research. In addition, it demonstrates how combining discourse analysis with noticing frameworks can deepen understanding of the reciprocal relationship between teacher professional learning and students mathematical discourse.

Keywords: lesson study, teacher noticing, mathematical discourse

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Framing A Desired Human Subjectivity In STEM Education: Personal And Collective Responsibility For Care And Justice

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Abstract

It has long been established that education and STEM education, are not neutral projects but rather are dynamic socio-cultural and ethical-political projects that change with every crisis in the economy (Arendt, 1954). At the same time, STEM education continues to be framed for a detached human observer within boundaries that have no little or no interface with the social sciences (Bazzul, 2023; Erduran, 2026; Günter et al., 2026). Here I critically scrutinise the framing of the social contract purpose of STEM education- to what extent the STEM education literature expresses this social contract and its implications for STEM teacher learning (Mooney Simmie & Moles, 2020).

Recent scoping reviews show that while STEM and STEAM education primarily focus on providing a desired 'pipeline' of talent for primacy of the economy and national security – abstract thinkers with entrepreneurial skillsets – there is far less attention paid to the relational (feminist) aims and collective responsibility for the social contract (critical consciousness), a person in relation with, self/Self, others/Others, technologies, and the planet/environment (Mooney Simmie, 2025; Mooney Simmie & Tolbert, 2025).

Here I draw from critical and feminist lenses provided by Braidotti (2020) and Roiniotti et al, (2025), to scrutinise the framing of subjectivity found in recent literature. Using guidance provided by Murphy and Costa (2022), a scoping review was undertaken in one journal *Cultural Studies in Science Education* from 2014 to 2025.

The preliminary findings illuminate the contested framing of the human-in-relation in the STEM literature and provide valuable insights into what is now needed if all children and young people are to be provided with a relevant STEM education ('why'), including access to content knowledge, theory and technological 'know'-how' and a felt sense of personal and collective responsibility for care, justice and sustainability (Bleier, 2024; Husseniús, 2014; Jupp, 2025; Levinson, 2017; Zouda, 2018).

Keywords: STEM education, human-in-relation, individual and collective responsibility

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Building Resilience through Partnership: The Role of Professional Learning Leaders in Primary Integrated STEM

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Abstract

As global crises necessitate interdisciplinary action, the human element of STEM education, specifically support structures for teachers, becomes paramount. While Ireland's revised primary STEM specification (DEY, 2025) emphasises integrated STEM (iSTEM), teachers often face barriers of confidence and isolation. This paper reports on

BRICS (Building a Real-World Integrated Curriculum in STEM), an iSTEM intervention involving teachers (n = 19), students (n = 338) aged 9 to 12, and Professional Learning Leaders (PLLs) from Oide (n = 2). Grounded in constructionist pedagogy and the Engineering Design Process, the intervention utilised LEGO Education robotics to facilitate hands-on inquiry.

This mixed-methods study revealed a complex reality. From quantitative analysis of T-STEM and S-STEM surveys, it emerged that teacher self-efficacy scores remained statistically stable. Qualitative data showed a marked increase in teacher confidence and engagement with STEM behaviours. Conversely, despite high initial student enthusiasm, post-intervention data indicated a slight decline in attitudes toward science and engineering. However, teachers reported significant growth in student collaboration and enthusiasm, highlighting the social dimensions of the iSTEM projects.

A central finding highlights the "human infrastructure" provided by PLLs. Their role in facilitating ongoing, collaborative professional support emerged as a critical enabler of iSTEM, counterbalancing constraints of time and resources. In the context of the STEM specification (DEY, 2025), this research argues that the future of STEM education depends on the resilient, professional communities we build around our teachers. By embedding practice-based, shared learning experiences, we can equip teachers to facilitate integrated STEM projects, which foster collaborative environments for their learners.

Keywords: integrated STEM; Education Robotics; Teacher Professional Learning; primary-level education

Primary Teachers' Mapping of Additive Word Problems to Number Sentences

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Abstract

In South Africa, national testing has shown word problems to be a key area of weakness amongst learners in early grade mathematics (Mostert, 2019). In response to this, as part of a design-based research project, we examined teachers' ability to work with additive word problems and their uptake of solution strategies introduced in a professional development course. This paper reports on 97 South African teachers who participated in a ten-month hybrid CPD programme aimed at developing their mathematical knowledge for teaching. This programme comprised of two full-day face-to-face workshops and

weekly support in the form of videos and interactive questions delivered via WhatsApp. The study is grounded in the literature on additive semantic structures (Vergnaud, 1982; Carpenter et al., 1999), which distinguishes additive situations according to the relationships between quantities and the position of the unknown. In this paper, we focus on tasks involving four additive structures: compare–difference unknown, compare–referent unknown, compare–quantity unknown, and separate–result unknown. A subsample of eight teachers completed task-based interviews. The interview tasks in focus in this paper required teachers to justify whether or not the three story problems could be modelled using the number sentence $63 - 25 = ?$. Findings show modest gains, with persistent structural challenges. On the written assessment, the compare–referent unknown item remained the most difficult for participants (pretest: 25.7% correct; post-test: 30.9% correct). The reasoning articulated in the interviews indicated teachers relied primarily on repeatedly reading the word problem as a solution strategy both in the pre- and post-interviews with minimal evidence of structural analysis or uptake of the representational models introduced in the professional development. The findings highlight the persistent challenge teachers face in mapping semantic structures to symbolic representations and point to the need to strengthen this aspect of the professional development course.

Keywords: Additive word problems, Number sentences, Semantic structure

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Speaking Mathematics: Oral Assessment in Analysis

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Abstract

The traditional form of assessment in mathematics in Ireland and the UK has long been the closed-book, timed, proctored, written examination (Iannone & Simpson, 2022). With the university campus closures that occurred as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the need for alternative assessments in mathematics was immediate and pressing (Ní Fhloinn & Fitzmaurice, 2025). This led to an expansion in the forms of assessment used in mathematics, with multiple-choice quizzes, online assessments, presentations, projects

and assignments becoming more common. However, the academic integrity of many of these assessments is vulnerable to the usage of generative artificial intelligence, whose advent into higher education has been unprecedented. In this environment, the introduction of oral examinations in mathematics, which are commonplace across Europe, was considered to be a valuable step forward. Switching a math module's assessment from written to oral examinations fosters deeper conceptual understanding, reduces barriers for students disadvantaged by traditional timed writing, and enables evaluation of reasoning over rote memorisation. Oral examinations allow real-time adjustment, rephrasing, and scaffolding without conferring unfair advantage. This approach also develops important skills such as articulation, critical thinking, and communication, preparing students for diverse academic and professional contexts. In this talk, we report on our approach, experiences and findings in introducing oral assessments into a first-year Analysis module in a mathematics degree programme in an Irish university. We outline our approach in scaffolding the introduction of the skill of "speaking mathematics" to our first-year students and provide insights into their perception of this new format of mathematical assessment. Here, we highlight both the positive and negative findings to present a balanced view of the student experience. We also outline the practical considerations, including the workload for the lecturer involved, and explore any evidence of improved student understanding as a result of this approach.

Keywords: Oral Assessment, First-Year, Mathematics

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Evaluating the Impact of a Role Models in pSTEM video Intervention on Post-Primary Students' Perceptions of pSTEM

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Abstract

Despite global and national policies promoting gender equality in STEM, a significant gender gap persists in mathematics-based subjects (pSTEM) (Slattery et al., 2023). While role model interventions have shown success in STEM contexts in Ireland, limited research focuses on their impact at post-primary level in pSTEM. To address this gap,

we investigate and evaluate the effectiveness of a video-based role model intervention. This intervention consists of a series of lessons designed to utilise 10 role model videos of contemporary Irish women working in pSTEM. These videos were designed based on the UNESCO ecological framework of gender in STEM (UNESCO, 2017), and an intervention consisting of a series of lessons was designed to use in tandem with the videos. First year post-primary students in one school were invited to participate in the research and asked to reflect on their perceptions of pSTEM before and after the intervention, incorporating a workbook and culminating in a project poster designed by each student. 15 learners volunteered to participate in the research, with parental consent. Data included pre- and post-intervention surveys, student workbooks, and project posters and were analysed utilising the UNESCO ecological framework. Findings indicate that these students entered post-primary education with distinct, gendered perceptions of pSTEM. During the intervention students' workbooks demonstrated a linguistic shift from viewing women as "not smart enough" to suggesting that women are "being told" they are not smart enough. The intervention significantly increased female students' intentions to pursue pSTEM pathways, with half of the female learners explicitly reported feeling "inspired" by the role models. Students highlighted teachers as a primary influence on their considerations of pSTEM subjects, particularly noting the impact of feedback and encouragement on their perceptions of success. While the low number of participants is a limitation of this study, the qualitative data suggests that a video-based intervention with contemporary role models can effectively mitigate harmful stereotypes and bolster female students' persistence in pSTEM.

Keywords: Role models, pSTEM, gender

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Investigating students' attitudes towards mathematics in socioeconomically disadvantaged schools

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Abstract

In Ireland socioeconomic disadvantage significantly impacts mathematics achievement, a disparity exacerbated by the "bonus points" policy for Higher Level Leaving Certificate mathematics (McCoy et al., 2019). While evidence from TIMMS suggests that students attending schools designated as socioeconomically disadvantaged are less likely to enjoy mathematics and have a more negative attitude towards the subject (e.g. Denner et al., 2025), little is understood about their attitudes towards mathematics more broadly. This research investigates the attitudes of post-primary learners in DEIS (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools) contexts, addressing a gap in understanding how disadvantage shapes learner dispositions towards the subject and, therefore, their achievement. Using an adapted Attitude Towards Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) (Lim & Chapman, 2013) with 552 learners across 10 DEIS schools, the study analysed their attitudes regarding Enjoyment, Self-Confidence and Value of Mathematics.

Findings indicate that male students demonstrate significantly higher self-confidence in mathematics than their female counterparts. Notably, having English as a first language did not influence self-confidence levels, suggesting dispositions towards and experiences of the subject were unrelated to language. The data also suggests that female students in urban schools reported a higher appreciation for the value of mathematics compared to other subgroups. Contextualizing these findings within broader trends, our data confirms a more negative attitude towards mathematics for learners in DEIS schools compared to their non-DEIS peers and suggests that structural barriers—such as limited access to Higher Level streams—combined with gendered self-concepts and a lack of understanding of the value of the subject beyond school, hinder STEM participation for disadvantaged youth, necessitating targeted interventions to address these entrenched inequities.

Keywords: Mathematics education; attitudes towards mathematics; socioeconomic disadvantage.

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Exploring Teachers' Use of Number Lines

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Abstract

Despite a growing focus on equity within the mathematics education research literature, the majority of children in the world do not meet minimum grade-level outcomes in mathematics, with up to 80 % of children in sub-Saharan Africa and parts of central and Southern Asia failing to meet the minimum proficiency level for their class level (Venkat & Adler, 2025). In the majority-marginalised context of South Africa, relevant gaps in the required mathematical knowledge for teaching have been identified, such as teachers' over reliance on concrete counting strategies at the expense of attention to mathematical structure that would facilitate more flexible reasoning (Venkat & Askew, 2018). Some interventions in South Africa have successfully used the number line in professional development activities to address gaps in students' and teachers' knowledge. Lovemore and Graven (2024) detail how the number line was successfully used to support preservice teachers in their teaching of efficient mental calculations, though in separate research Mathews and Prinsloo (2025) note the need for more structured pedagogical scaffolding for teachers to support effective number line use.

The data reported on in this study is drawn from a larger IRC-funded research and development project in South Africa which aims to enhance student outcomes by increasing teachers' mathematical knowledge for teaching. Specifically, we examine segments of individual teachers' task-based interviews, pre- and post- professional development, where they use number lines to demonstrate and/or calculate multidigit addition and subtraction problems. We use the Pirie and Kieran (1994) model of growth in mathematical understanding to identify the levels at which teachers are operating and will discuss the phenomenon of teachers 'folding back' (Martin, 2008) to earlier levels of understanding. More generally, we will discuss the levels of understanding teachers need to teach effectively with specific mathematical representations.

Keywords: Number Line, Marginalised, Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching

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Instructional Vision on Entry to Initial Teacher Education

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Abstract

It has long been noted that preservice teachers' (PSTs) previous learning experiences, or the 'apprenticeship of observation' (Lortie, 1975), serves to shape the beliefs they hold and the practices they enact. Initial teacher education (ITE) must address both the knowledge needed to teach, and dispositional aspects of teaching such as beliefs, attitudes and affect (Jacobsen, 2017). While the research on the relationship between teacher beliefs and practice is complex (Skott, 2014), beliefs can be understood as a lens through which teachers interpret the world (Phillip, 2007). This is of particular importance in ITE where PSTs are likely being inducted into enacting non-traditional teaching practices, which they may have limited direct experience of. In this research, we used the notion of instructional vision, or images of ideal classroom practice (Munter 2014) as a means of investigating the conceptions held by PSTs on entry to ITE.

A questionnaire was administered to 458 PSTs in the initial weeks of their first year of ITE. The findings reported here are drawn from an analysis of three open-ended questions where participants were asked to describe "the best" teaching they could imagine. Responses were dual-coded by two researchers using the Vision for High-Quality Mathematics Instruction (VHQMI) instrument (Munter, 2014, p. 586). This identified a numerical level for each PST for each of the dimensions: engagement, mathematical tasks, pattern and structure of talk, and role of the teacher. We will present descriptive statistics such as mean scores for VHQMI dimensions alongside examples of the PSTs responses which describe PSTs' instructional vision. More students were scored at a higher level for tasks and engagement than the other two components. Possible reasons

for this will be discussed and implications for ITE will be outlined, such as an increased focus on the pedagogical practice of maths talk.

Keywords: Preservice teachers, Beliefs, Instructional Vision

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Spatial Thinking in the Irish Primary Curriculum

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Abstract

Spatial thinking is recognised as a cognitive ability that aids success in education with a link between high spatial ability and academic achievement, particularly success in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education (Hegarty, 2010; Uttal et al., 2013). However, studies have shown that spatial thinking is often implicitly included rather than explicitly identified in curricula. This raises questions about whether, and how, education systems are prepared to support the development of spatial thinking. This is particularly pertinent in the Irish context where studies have shown Ireland to have one of the biggest gaps in scores on spatial related items on the PISA assessment (OECD, 2022). In this study, we explored the potential development of spatial ability in the recently published STEM specification of the Irish primary curriculum (DoE, 2023). We conducted a qualitative content analysis of STEM learning outcomes using the 3x3 matrix framework proposed by Lin et al. (2024). Lin's et al framework categorises the potential spatial content of the curriculum into two dimensions: visual representation (graphical, pictorial, manufactured) and epistemic function (conceptual, procedural, spatial citizenship). We applied this framework to identify where and how spatial thinking may occur in the STEM specification of the Irish curriculum and how it may be developed across the four stages of the primary age range. At this time of significant

curriculum change in Ireland, our findings will serve to increase awareness of the potential for developing spatial abilities within the new curriculum specifications and may highlight gaps at particular ages or in different subject areas. In addition, we are expecting that our findings will inform ongoing teacher professional development and curriculum support materials. Our research can contribute to discussions on curriculum design and offers evidence that could be used in future research on spatial thinking and educational development in Ireland.

Keywords: Spatial thinking, Curriculum, STEM

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STEM Eyes: Spatial Thinking in Primary STEM Education

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Abstract

Spatial thinking is used widely across many disciplines but is often linked with Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) where achievement on spatial measures has been found to be a predictor of success in the STEM fields (UNESCO, 2017). Atit et al. (2020) argue that fundamental spatial problems increase in complexity in STEM contexts, but experts rely less on spatial skills due to domain knowledge. They suggest that teaching should address both fundamental spatial skills, or cross-cutting concepts, and discipline-relevant spatial skills to foster disciplinary achievement. In the context of recent curricular reform in Ireland, this paper explores the extent to which spatial thinking is made explicit in the new specification for STEM education at primary level (DoE, 2025).

Using content analysis (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008), relevant learning outcomes of the STEM specifications was examined for evidence of the spatial skills in the typology of

Newcombe and Shipley (2015). Newcombe and Shipley's (2015) typology identifies spatial skills relevant to young children and includes 6 intrinsic spatial skills, e.g., disembedding, categorisation, and 5 extrinsic spatial skills, e.g., alignment, perspective taking. Our analysis shows that while these spatial skills are present in some areas of the specification, notably the mathematics learning outcomes for the 'Shape and Space' strand; many learning outcomes do not explicitly refer to spatial ideas and may be interpreted in ways that do intentionally address spatial thinking. Our results include attention to learning outcomes which reference 'STEM eyes'. This is a key phrase in the Nature of STEM strand and may be interpreted as connected with the spatial skill of disembedding. Equally, it may be interpreted as referring to dispositional aspects of adopting a STEM perspective on the world.

Keywords: Spatial Thinking; Curriculum; STEM

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Beyond Floating and Sinking: Narrative-Led Engineering in the Primary Science Classroom

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Abstract

Background

NCCA Research Report No. 10 (Varley et al., 2008) identifies a "cause for concern" regarding the 'Energy and Forces' strand. Findings indicate pupil engagement is often limited to "floating and sinking," with rare exposure to levers, pulleys, or friction. This deficit restricts pupils' ability to engage meaningfully in design thinking. While STEM encompasses broad problem-solving, solutions requiring a built artefact necessitate

mechanical principles. Much like mathematical fluency relies on number sense, a foundational grasp of mechanics is essential for pupils to move beyond trial and error toward intentional design.

Method

This project employs Design-Based Research (DBR), centring on a narrative-led resource: a modular wooden kit which I designed, paired with a storybook, Henry's Piano, which I wrote and illustrated. By physically interacting with the kit, pupils develop an "embodied toolkit of resources" grounded in sensorimotor experiences (Thomas Jha et al., 2020). This physical grounding allows even the youngest pupils to "think" and "talk" science through gesture and action before transitioning to formal data literacy.

Findings

The resource tasks pupils with moving a piano using simple machines such as levers and pulley systems. Through "Fair Test" protocols, pupils measure force in Newtons (N), scaffolding a transition to quantitative literacy. Observations suggest the narrative anchor lowers the "threshold of entry" for physics, promoting learner agency. Furthermore, the structured nature of the kit provided a clear pedagogical framework for teachers, building pedagogical confidence in a strand where many self-report a lack of expertise and prior training.

Implications

By positioning pupils as "protagonists" (Cho, 2024), the project validates "story-driven embodied play" as a necessary "on-ramp" for difficult physics. Henry's Piano offers a scalable model for fostering "Engineering Habits of Mind," ensuring 'Energy and Forces' becomes a robust, accessible component of primary education.

Keywords: Embodied Learning, Narrative-led Inquiry, Primary Science

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"I wouldn't have thought about the science. I didn't realise half of what was going on!" - Sociodramatic co-play as a pedagogical approach for early STEM learning.

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Abstract

Research suggests that the use of sociodramatic co-play, in which educators play alongside young children to support their play and learning, can be an effective pedagogical approach to supporting early STEM learning (Fleer, 2019). Sociodramatic play is particularly motivating for young children and is crucial to the development of executive function and self-regulation, symbolic thinking and imagination, all of which are essential for STEM learning (Bodrova and Leong, 2015; Whitebread & O'Sullivan, 2012). Sociodramatic co-play allows educators to pursue children's inquiries with them, whilst taking opportunities to support the STEM learning that emerges during play. Co-play must be conducted sensitively by educators, who identify and take advantage of learning opportunities that arise, whilst allowing children to maintain ownership and control of their play (Pramling Samuelsson & Björklund, 2023). This type of play has been shown to allow for more inclusive participation in STEM learning for all children, but particularly for girls, who historically have been underrepresented in this area (Fleer, 2021).

This presentation will report on an 8-month Professional Learning intervention for 6 highly experienced educators with a range of qualifications, within a cross-community Early Childhood setting. The intervention sought to support the educators to learn about sociodramatic co-play, early Science and early Maths in order to be able to use sociodramatic co-play to support children's learning in these curriculum areas. The intervention involved workshops, mentoring and video analysis of practice, and data collection involved both audio- and video-recordings of educators and children.

Initial findings suggest that participation in the Professional Learning intervention supported educators to understand that sociodramatic co-play is important for children's learning, and that opportunities for Science and Maths conceptual and process learning can be identified and supported within that space.

Keywords: STEM, Sociodramatic play, Pedagogy

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How Irish Primary Teachers Performed on Spatial Ability Tasks and Its Relationship with STEM Classroom Engagement

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Abstract

Spatial ability supports achievement in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) by enabling mental rotation, visualisation, and perspective-taking (Hegarty, 2010; Uttal et al., 2013). Although researchers have extensively examined spatial ability in students, they have rarely investigated teachers' spatial performance, particularly in Ireland. It therefore remains unclear how Irish primary teachers perform across different spatial domains and whether spatial ability relates to STEM classroom engagement.

In this study, we examined Irish primary teachers' performance across the spatial spectrum and investigated its relationship with STEM engagement in teaching. Following Uttal et al.'s (2013) 2×2 typology, which emphasises the need to assess both intrinsic–extrinsic and static–dynamic dimensions of spatial processing, we selected tasks that captured small-scale intrinsic-dynamic and large-scale spatial abilities. Teachers completed a computerised Mental Rotation Task (Shepard & Metzler, 1971) and a Spatial Orientation Task (Friedman et al., 2020). We measured STEM engagement using a structured self-reporting instrument that assessed the frequency and type of STEM-related activities integrated into classroom practice. We also collected demographic information, including years of teaching experience, class level being taught, and language medium of the teachers' school. We analysed the data using multiple regression to examine whether the teachers' spatial ability predicted STEM engagement.

This study generated the first empirical dataset on Irish primary school teachers' spatial ability. By examining spatial performance alongside classroom engagement, we build on

research carried out in other countries on individual differences in education and their potential relevance for STEM teaching practice. There is a good deal of research that has been carried out on this topic and we intend to extend this by introducing the Irish perspective to the database of information.

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Does going digital change the clock? Comparing an online and paper-based assessment

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Abstract

Teachers use a wide range of digital tools in the junior cycle mathematics classroom, although recent reports indicate they are used primarily for resource sharing and creating instructional materials rather than for assessing students (Karakolidis et al., 2025). While online assessment was previously limited in the Irish post-primary context due to a lack of available digital devices, recently access has increased significantly. Within this evolving digital landscape, there is a need to consider how established assessment practices translate across formats.

A standardised criterion referenced assessment known as a screener for initial algebra was developed as a pen and paper formative assessment, designed to support teachers by providing a profile of students' knowledge and highlighting common errors (Healy OBrien, 2021). Currently, an online version of the screener is being developed and an important aspect of this is investigating its validity and reliability. Existing research suggests that students typically complete online mathematics assessments more quickly than equivalent paper-based formats (McClelland & Cuevas, 2020). This raises the question of the extent to which students allocate comparable time and cognitive effort to online assessment items as they do to pen and paper tasks.

This research investigates the differences in students' perceptions of time adequacy and cognitive effort across online and pen and paper formats. This mixed-methods study

draws on quantitative and qualitative data from the administration of both versions of the screener (pen and paper n= 555, online n=93). Pearson's Chi-square test of independence will examine the relationship between the groups responses when asked if they had enough time to complete the screener, alongside qualitative analysis of students' comments on task item difficulty and the overall screener, providing insights into cognitive effort. This study contributes to understanding how digital assessment formats may influence student engagement and performance in the junior cycle mathematics classroom.

Keywords: Initial Algebra, Assessment, Junior Cycle

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Bridging the Maths Gap - Initial Design of Mathematics-Focused Tutorial Worksheets for First-Year Undergraduate Physics Students

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Abstract

The underpreparedness of first-year students in mathematics across science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) programmes at universities has been well reported (Hourigan and O'Donoghue, 2007). Faulkner et al. (2021) found that students' ability to apply basic mathematical concepts to solve problems in context is not as strong as their procedural ability to solve mathematics questions. Mathematics is reported to be one of the main contributors to low retention rates in STEM subjects (Bourn, 2007). In an attempt to address this, we are developing mathematics-focused worksheets for algebra-

based physics tutorials that aim to support students in their transition to university physics. Observations of students during a pilot phase of this research indicate that students struggle with numerical problems encountered in algebra-based physics. This poster presents our initial design of pilot worksheets. The worksheets adopt a guided-inquiry structure and are designed to encourage group work with the tutor acting as a facilitator. The questions are staged to allow students to work independently within groups and recognise where their exact difficulties lie when solving numerical problems. A strong emphasis is on students activating mathematical skills in a physics context, without neglecting conceptual aspects, in contrast to many other research-informed approaches which tend to focus on concepts isolated from procedural mathematical skills (e.g. McDermott et al., 1998). The worksheet design embeds mathematical skills which we see as essential for physics, including rearranging formulae, working with vectors trigonometrically, drawing useful diagrams/representations from given information, and using units appropriately. These worksheets have been trialled with a small number of students. Looking ahead, we aim to scale these tutorials to meet the needs of 400+ students enrolled in algebra-based physics modules. We will also explore factors influencing students to not attend tutorials, to mitigate these, and to look into the effectiveness of the worksheets.

Keywords: Mathematics/Physics Education, First-year Algebra-Based Physics, Tutorial Worksheets Design.

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Do you want to make a battery? Insights from the development and evaluation of an accessible STEM public engagement activity

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Abstract

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 ensures access to clean and affordable energy, which is key to agriculture, business, communications, education, healthcare and transportation. Central to this are batteries, which now dominate our lives. However, they are poorly understood, leading to misconceptions.[1] There are many well-known difficulties associated with providing hands-on science activities outside the lab and other formal learning environments.[2][3] Here, a simple multi-disciplinary battery activity has been developed for public engagement with accessibility incorporated by design. Participants build a historic Voltaic Pile from aluminium foil, Play-Doh© and copper coated coins. This sustainable battery can power a low voltage LED (light emitting diode) or an alarm on a wristwatch for visually impaired participants.

A “micro-workshop” format with everyone seated (facilitators and participants) provided more time for two-way conversation, prevented talking down to participants, and facilitated wheelchair users. A “Front-of-House” leader also controlled the crowds, assigned participants to tables and managed breaks. The benefits afforded by outdoor learning for developing curiosity and interest in science has also been explored through different event formats.

The use of a ‘Smiley Stand’ with ‘emojis’ for gathering participant feedback was also successfully deployed with over 8k responses to date. The feedback has helped us tailor the language and emphasis for different events and audiences, as well as identifying quiet periods for those in the ASD community. Overall, it was found that the activity encouraged two-way conversations between the participants and the facilitators, with overwhelmingly positive feedback received. Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT) is normally used by retailers, with 85% considered excellent. This activity has received an unprecedented overall CAST score of 93%, which also varies by type of event. The activity has also impacted the facilitators’ own view of STEM careers, with many citing that these activities re-ignited their own interest in science.

Keywords: Public Engagement Communication Engaged Research

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Pride and Inspiration: Reigniting the spark in early career researchers

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Abstract:

There is strong evidence to suggest that doctoral programmes can contribute to negative mental health and career outlook (Evans, 2020 and Bergyall, 2024), with some losing their enthusiasm for science, prompting the need for intervention (O'Donoghue, 2024). Through a semi-structured programme, our science PhD researchers are offered flexible modules to fit around their research. The 'Science Communication' Module has formalised education and public engagement (EPE) training and in 2015 we embarked on a complete redesign through a co-creation process. Now, over a decade later, we have trained nearly one hundred PhD's and gathered extensive feedback along the way. Since then, this short module has continued to develop iteratively to become a unique and desirable opportunity to hone a variety of skills through 'work experience', unique team projects and formal lectures in Presentation Skills, Science Education Theory and Self-Reflection.

Assessment is through a self-reflective journal and a team project presentation. The team projects involve developing and testing new initiatives for public audiences and presenting their ideas to a panel of experts for critical discussion. In some cases, this is their first time presenting, providing a neutral platform away from their research to hone their presentation skills. This talk will outline the module structure, the co-creation process, and the feedback received from focus groups, interviews, and surveys. Emerging themes from the self-reflection journals will also be discussed against a backdrop of pre-, during and post- COVID shutdowns. The participants identified unique benefits to the module compared to other available opportunities, with some stating that it reminded them why they chose a career in science in the first place. The talk will wrap up with a look at some of impacts achieved to date as well as a look towards the future.

Keywords: Training PhDs Communication Professional Development

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Action Video Games as a Form of Spatial Training: Comparing Virtual Reality to Traditional Computers with Relation to Mathematics Ability.

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Abstract

Research has indicated that training spatial skills can transfer to math performance (Hawes et al., 2022). Interestingly, Action Videogames (AVGs) have shown to be an effective method of spatial training (Feng et al., 2007, Novak & Tassel, 2015). However, it is unknown whether the medium through which AVGs are played affects the extent that spatial and maths abilities improve. For Science, Technology, Engineering, Maths (STEM) students, spatial skills are correlated with course retention (Sithole et al., 2017). Therefore, spatial training seems important for these educational areas in a world that needs them more annually. Many studies examine a limited range of spatial skills, do not investigate maths, or focus exclusively on computer-based training. Therefore, the empirical question is: Does Virtual Reality (VR) training using AVGs yield greater spatial and maths benefits than computer-based training?

To address this question, we assessed a broader range of spatial skills alongside maths and investigated whether the medium through which AVGs are played affected the extent that spatial skills and maths could be improved. Following a pre-post experimental design, 38 STEM students in Ireland participated in one 40-minute training session, chosen due to prior literature and academic time constraints. The experimental group used VR with motion-controllers while the control group used a laptop and controller. We measured spatial skills following the 2x2 typology (Uttal et al., 2013): a Mental Rotation Task (MRT; Shepard & Metzler, 1971) for intrinsic and Spatial Orientation Task (SOT; Friedman et al., 2019) for extrinsic skills. We used an addition-task to test transfer to fluid math competency, and collected covariate data (i.e., game experience and VR induced symptoms) using a survey. Results showed an increase in accuracy and decrease

in reaction time for the MRT across both groups, indicating an improvement in intrinsic-dynamic spatial skills, however the difference between groups was non-significant.

Keywords: STEM, Virtual Reality, Spatial Skills, Maths, Action Videogames

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Symposium: The hare's corner in the classroom: The role of STEM education in addressing the biodiversity crisis

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Abstract

Our education system plays a key role in supporting a thriving society and, in the context of the climate and biodiversity crises, is fundamental to supporting and developing a collective approach to nature protection and restoration. The 'Hare's Corner' is an old farming expression for the corner of land which was left to nature, and we utilise this phrase in the classroom context to highlight how space might be found in the curriculum to leave to nature.

Utilising the context of the new EU Nature Restoration Regulation, the development of Ireland's National Nature Restoration Plan, and the fact that nature knows no borders,

this symposium will consider current education policies and practices and outline opportunities to improve nature education and ecological literacy. Children's connections to nature will be key to such work.

Philosophically, one of the barriers to embedding nature education and ecological literacy in the formal curriculum is the man/nature dualism that promulgates the human's position as dominator of the natural world, ignoring the rule of natural law where man is but one part of an interconnected whole (Dewey 1910). This symposium will illustrate how the division between man and nature is evident in science textbooks, government policies and teacher perspectives on biology education. The one-sided use and abuse of the natural world has led to a biodiversity crisis that threatens the existence of all life on earth. Bringing an ethic of care into how we teach about the natural world would seem like a reasonable response to this existential threat, yet care work is itself often dismissed as voluntary work that is done in leftover time with leftover energy and is neglected by a governing system that is underpinned by economic ideals grounded in colonialism and built on capitalism (Lynch, 2022). While there are educational organisations that promote biodiversity, such as the Irish Schools Sustainability Network, their work relies on volunteerism and sits outside the formal education system.

The first paper in this symposium will explore the prevalence of a human-centric approach to education curricula and policies. While education systems are an ideal place in which a love and appreciation for nature can be nurtured, education is often left out of wider policy considerations. In tandem, however, education policy now promotes the principles of human-capital to the point that it is deeply embedded into the language of global education, with Science Education seen as a gateway for the development of *Homo Economicus* (Lynch, 2022).

The second paper will report on a study undertaken with in-service and pre-service biology teachers between Queens University Belfast and DCU, which mapped botany and biodiversity in the curriculum and explored teachers' views on teaching plant biology. Biology literally means 'the study of life' but, following on from the first paper, it has become more about the study of human life. This study will share some concerning findings of the anthropocentric nature of our science and biology curricula.

The final paper explores the opportunities and challenges for the new STEM Education specification for primary and special schools (DEY 2025) in supporting the biodiversity crisis. There are opportunities for children to have direct experiences in and with nature, a key factor in environmental care in adulthood (Chawla 2007), however there are also challenges associated with primary teacher confidence in teaching about nature. Implications for Initial Teacher Education are highlighted.

A discussion incorporating these three papers in the context of new national and international laws and the potential of education to contribute to the future lives of learners will conclude the symposium.

Keywords: Nature restoration, Biodiversity education, STEM education

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Paper 1: What would happen if we replace economy with ecology in STEM policy?

Abstract

The first paper in this symposium will explore the prevalence of a human-centric approach to education curricula and policies. While education systems are an ideal place in which a love and appreciation for nature can flourish, education is often left out of wider policy considerations. In tandem, however, education policy now promotes the principles of human-capital to the point that it is deeply embedded into the language of global education, with Science Education in particular seen as a gateway for the development of *Homo Economicus* (Lynch, 2022). Using content analysis, this paper will consider the influence of economic priorities on key STEM education policies in Ireland and on policy regarding nature restoration, linking with how national Science and Biology curricula have narrowed to include what is deemed worthwhile for the economy, to the detriment of knowledge about the natural world (Monbiot and Hutchinson, 2024) Using a theoretical framework derived from the work of Kimmerer, it will also argue for an ecological approach to science education that prioritises eco-literacy in the curriculum to counterbalance the dominant economic model. Knowledge of our interconnectedness with nature is the first step to restoring the division between humans and nature (Kimmerer, 2013)

Keywords: Ecological education, STEM policy

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Paper 2: Plant blindness among our young post primary teachers – the death of botany

Abstract

The second paper reports on a botany focused study undertaken with pre-service biology teachers between Queens University Belfast and DCU. Biology means ‘the study of life’ but, following on from the first paper, it has become more about the study of human life. A recent paper from Stroud et al (2022) identified a problem with ‘plant blindness’ among the general population, which is a cognitive bias where people fail to notice, appreciate or understand the importance of plants in their daily life. They formed a direct connection between plant blindness and the erosion of botany from the school curriculum in the UK. O’Neill and Kerr (2025) recently found a similar erosion of botanical content from Irish (North and South) biology curricula. This presentation reports on thematically analysed findings from a survey given to pre-service biology teachers from DCU and QUB (n=41), that found a lack of training around botanical content among PSTs and as a result has a lack of confidence in teaching plant science. A cohort of these PSTs (n=20) took part in four workshops which were focused on botany and ecology. They were asked to teach plant science when they were out on school placement and to maintain reflective journals as a part of this. Findings from a thematic analysis of the journals showed wider issues with a lack of spaces and opportunities to teach botany, and a heavy influence of terminal assessment on what PSTs could and could not teach. The lack of botany learning in schools has a knock-on effect on the number of entrants to STEM programmes that choose to study botany, resulting in a dearth of botanists and ecologists at a time when they are most needed.

Keywords: Plant blindness, Early career teachers, Initial teacher education

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Paper 3: Opportunities and challenges for bringing nature into primary school classrooms

Abstract

The final paper explores the opportunities and challenges for the new STEM Education specification for primary and special schools (DEY 2025) in supporting the biodiversity crisis. There are clear opportunities for children to have direct experiences in and with nature, which has been identified as a key factor in environmental care in adulthood

(Chawla 2007). This is in line with the Primary Curriculum Framework which has learning environments, indoors and outdoors, as one of its key principles of learning, teaching and assessment. This recognises the importance of diverse environments to stimulate and support their learning across the curriculum. Additionally, outcomes associated with plant observation, identification, classification, eco systems, interdependence and biodiversity are evident and welcome in the STEM Education specification, as is the connection with materials and their impact on the environment. However, these are firmly rooted in the science strands of the Science, Technology and Engineering Education specification. Furthermore, in terms of the 'nature of STEM' and 'STEM integration' there are missed opportunities to support nature connection. This raises the question about the role of nature in STEM Education policy, which can focus on 'industry', 'workforce' and 'research and development' to the detriment of the 'society' or 'environment' piece. Ultimately, these challenges and opportunities are set against a backdrop of a key challenge associated with primary teacher confidence in teaching about nature and (non-human) living things. This directly links with the lack of botany in biology curricula highlighted in the second paper and the human centric focus in curricula and policy explored in the first paper. These opportunities and challenges will be explored and the implications for initial teacher education will be highlighted, in particular the role of teachers as influential role models in supporting environmental stewardship (Chawla 2007) and the importance of subject expertise.

Keywords: Primary education, Nature, STEM integration

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Exploring the Affective Domain of Learning in Technology Education, utilising a Qualitative Modified Delphi Study.

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Abstract

This research investigates the affective domain in Technology education, examining how the representation of emotions, values, and motivation within the curriculum shapes students' learning, alongside teachers' professional learning, pedagogical judgement, and perceptions of technological capability. Drawing on the perspectives of experienced

teachers, pre-service teachers, and experts in the field, the study advocates for balanced recognition of the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of learning, fostering social and emotional development while supporting the development of technological capability (Buckley et al., 2018). Drawing on Krathwohl et al.'s (1964) taxonomy of the affective domain, alongside Biesta's (2010, 2017) theory of subjectification and the philosophical accounts of technology as a value-laden human activity advanced by Mitcham (1994) and Gibson (2008), the wider research conceptualises affective learning as integral to authentic technological practice. This framing is further supported by Immordino-Yang's (2016) neuroscientific account of the inseparability of emotion and cognition in meaningful learning. Earlier phases employed Constructivist Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006, 2014) to analyse curriculum documents, questionnaires, and focus groups, generating themes including affective practice, constraint, emotional safety, engagement, resilience, well-being, teacher development, and life beyond school.

To refine and extend these themes, a qualitative modified Delphi design is employed. Unlike a classical Delphi, this study presents panel members with structured statements derived from prior qualitative findings. In Round 1, participants review statements, indicate their level of agreement using a Likert scale, and provide comments, amendments, and concise professional rationales based on their experience and context. Responses are analysed using constant comparison (Charmaz, 2014) to identify convergence, divergence, and conceptual refinement. In Round 2, revised statements and anonymised panel feedback are returned for further endorsement and clarification. Findings will identify areas of convergence and divergence, contributing to a theoretically robust and practice-informed framework for understanding affective learning in technology education.

Keywords: Affective, Modified Delphi Study, Technology Education

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Electronics for Climate Creativity

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Abstract

This conference poster presents reflection of a second-year teaching module, *Electronics for Climate Creativity*, undertaken by undergraduate students across the Faculty of Film, Art and Creative Technologies at the Institute of Art, Design and Technology (IADT), Dun Laoghaire. Responding to the discourse on climate change, sustainability, and environmental responsibility, students taking the module critically engage with these themes, producing artistic or design-led artefacts, enhanced through coding and electronic technologies.

The teaching team has delivered practical courses at the intersection of electronics, art, design, and climate themes for several decades, taking a constructivist pedagogical approach to modular design.

The module is structured around three interconnected pedagogical strands: thematic contextualisation, design thinking, and creative artistic practice. Students begin by researching climate change, sustainability, and environmental issues through case studies and discussion. They then participate in workshops on design thinking and artistic practice, supporting idea generation, concept visualisation, and critical reflection on the ecological and social implications of their creative choices. In parallel, students develop technical proficiency with the Arduino microcontroller platform, integrating sensors, motors, lighting, and audio components into expressive or solution-driven prototypes.

A focused design thinking workshop for the students and their counterparts in a business programme, was delivered by the Rediscovery Centre—Ireland's National Centre for a Circular Economy. Additionally, there was a visit to an IADT supported exhibition in art, design and technology in the climate action space, at the Royal Hibernian Academy.

The detailed work of the module involved student teams pitching their project ideas to develop prototypes responding to core themes and then building prototypes, supported through guidance and troubleshooting support. Students also developed reflective journals, supported by tutorials. The poster will reflect on all stages of the module, summarising student engagement in the module, via their learning journals and project presentations, in a constructivist pedagogical context.

Keywords: Sustainability, Creativity, Technology

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From Capstone to Career: Navigating the Uncertainty of Open-Source Robotics in the Engineering Design Process

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Abstract

Engineering education requires the development of design skills alongside the application of STEM knowledge. Many undergraduate engineering programmes include a final year (capstone) project which addresses design learning outcomes and provides experience in addressing open-ended problems which prepare graduates for working in the engineering profession (Dym et al., 2005). This style of learning presents challenges and opportunities for students to develop resilience in dealing with uncertainty when there is not a single correct solution or approach.

Within engineering at university level, the increasing cost of proprietary hardware and software presents challenges for Departments, which open-source environments can address. However, this can introduce additional complexity for students; requiring specialised digital literacy skills when conducting research. During their studies, students engage with many open-source communities of practice where documentation can be complex, fragmented and where anyone can contribute solutions (often referred to as a 'glass box' as opposed to a 'black box'). This requires students to develop and deploy information literacy and critical thinking skills as they decide which sources are reliable (Garritano, 2013); resilience as learning takes place through constructive failure (Kapur, 2008); and moving to becoming a full part of these communities of practice through developing digital agency and contributing to knowledge.

This reflective case study presents the first-person student experience of using a modular open-source educational robotics platform (Mirte: developed by TU Delft (Netherlands))

to complete a final year Mechatronic Engineering project in social robots. During the academic year, the journey from novice/reader to expert/author is explored as part of engineering identity development through a situated learning perspective. This work addresses the research question “How does engagement with open-source communities of practice develop professional resilience and digital literacy during an undergraduate final year engineering project?” The experiences are transferrable to other open-source technologies and STEM disciplines.

Keywords: Open-source, Robotics Education, Engineering Design

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Narrative and Empathy as Engineering Design Constraints: A Mechatronics Capstone Project Case Study

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Abstract

Narrative and storytelling have been found to improve comprehension of STEM subjects as it reduces cognitive overload and improves engagement when communicating with non-experts (Dahlstrom, 2014). STEAM is an acronym used to centre the importance of Art and creativity within STEM subjects. While at school there is a focus on incorporating the arts in the curriculum (Perignat & Katz-Buonincontro, 2019), within undergraduate engineering courses there is arguably a strict focus on technical content and design. A year-long capstone project in the final year provides an opportunity for students to showcase their engineering design skills while working on an open-ended problem and engaging in design-based learning.

This capstone project required the design and build of mechatronic systems to be used within an escape room for transition-year students to engage in a STEM experience. Engineering elements included a combinational digital logic system to support

computational thinking, and a Geneva gear providing a mechanism to dispense scents to enhance immersion.

This work uses an integrated reflection cycle approach (Bassot, 2023) incorporating a professional conversation where the undergraduate student and supervisor reflect upon and discuss challenges and opportunities of making art (narrative, theme and immersion) an engineering design constraint which carries parity with technical requirements. For example, project assessment criteria prioritize technical sophistication, while stakeholder requirements carry lower weightings. The researchers reflect on challenges overcoming the perceived priority of technical requirements in engineering, recognising their own identity as engineers shaping their perspectives.

This work contributes to the literature on STEAM education by providing insights into enacting STEAM in a final year engineering project and reflecting how undergraduate students can be supported to practice empathetic design; where engineers step outside of their own experiences and empathize with the people they are designing for.

Keywords: Empathetic Design, Escape Rooms, STEAM Education

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Visualizing Potential: Design and Evaluation of a ‘Voltage First’ Approach to an Undergraduate Introductory Electrical Circuit Curriculum

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Abstract

Fundamental electrical circuit concepts can often be misunderstood by students (Shipstone et al., 1988). Research looking at reimaging the curriculum to consider a ‘voltage first’ approach can improve learning outcomes and reduce student misconceptions in secondary schools (Burde et al., 2022). This work discusses the redesign and implementation of a first year undergraduate electrical circuits module taken by all students on the Common Entry into Engineering programme at Dublin City

University (DCU), using the voltage first approach. The analogy of air pressure was used to model voltage as 'electrical pressure' that gives rise to current and is affected by resistance, which was then developed into the properties of voltage in parallel and series circuits using a visual and qualitative approach before incorporating ohm's law calculations. A modernised concept inventory questionnaire (reDIRECT) was used to quantify student understanding (n=91) (Ridgway et al., 2025). The DCU cohort mean (34%) for the survey was lower than the reported findings for the original diagnostic (DIRECT) undergraduate mean (44%) and more comparable with the high school mean (36%) (Engelhardt & Beichner, 2004). However the DCU student scores for questions examining voltage within circuits were much closer to previously reported undergraduate results (DCU = 33%, DIRECT = 34%). A similar improvement was observed for items examining understanding of visual circuits with series and parallel connections (DCU = 52%, DIRECT = 54%). The improved performance on these objectives compared to the overall mean indicates the initial success of the curriculum in supporting students to understand voltage concepts.

Keywords: Electronics, Voltage, Electrical Circuits

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From outcast to outreach: examining the effects of a spatialised STEM outreach on children's STEM motivation

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Abstract

Spatial ability is linked to participation and achievement in STEM (Zhu et al., 2023). Yet its role in informal outreach, typically oriented toward nurturing motivation and interest, remains underexplored. This study investigates whether a spatialised STEM outreach activity is associated with changes in children's motivation. The research adopts a

multiple case study with participants aged 8-12. Within each case, three iterative workshop cycles are implemented to progressively refine the activity, guided by the Knowledge Transfer Framework (Gagnier & Fisher, 2020) and co-designed with outreach providers (Engeström, 2001; Engeström & Sannino, 2016). Each cycle involves a new cohort (≈ 20 participants per cycle; ≈ 60 per case). Using a QUAL-dominant embedded mixed-methods design, participant-observation notes and artefacts (photographs/sketches) constitute the evidentiary core, while pre/post measures (Spatial Reasoning Instrument and Science Motivation Questionnaire-II) provide corroborative, directional indicators in each cycle. At the time of submission, data collection and analysis are in progress and will be completed by May. Findings from this study would extend spatial ability literature into informal STEM by 'spatialisation' within outreach activity design and offering emerging design principles for STEM outreach practitioners seeking to enhance children's motivation through spatialised outreach.

Keywords: Spatial ability, Spatial intervention, Informal STEM education

Lesson Study as a Catalyst for Innovative Future Professional Learning of STEM Teacher Educators

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Abstract

Although teacher professional learning has gained increasing attention, there is a lack of research exploring the professional learning of teacher educators and the approaches that support it (Schipper et al., 2022). The timely introduction of the first Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) curriculum (NCCA, 2025) in Ireland provided an opportunity for a group of teacher educators to reflect and refocus their practices through collaboration, aiming to enhance their practice and provide meaningful STEM learning experiences for preservice teachers.

Over the last two decades, Lesson Study (LS) has become increasingly popular, extending from its origins in Japan to classrooms worldwide, where it is recognised for its significant contributions to teacher professional development (Vermunt et al., 2019). Despite the advantages associated with LS, few studies have examined the potential benefits of LS in teacher educators' professional learning (Schipper et al., 2022).

In response this study explores STEM teacher educators' ($n=4$), participation in LS with the goal of enhancing their teaching and student experiences in a second-year science module for preservice teacher. The participants (2 mathematics TEs, 2 science TEs) represent varying experiences in terms of collaboration, LS practices, and years'

experience in the sector. The LS, conducted in Autumn 2025, focused on developing a science education tutorial (relating to the concept of Forces) to support the content and pedagogical knowledge development of preservice primary teachers. The TEs completed a LS cycle consisting of an iterative cycle of study, plan, implement, and reflect. Throughout the process, data were generated through planning documentation, fieldnotes, individual TE reflections, group recorded reflective discussions and focus group interview.

This research illustrates several opportunities offered by the LS model for TEs, including, the role of self-efficacy, the deepening of pedagogical understanding, such as balancing inquiry-based learning with explicit teaching, engaging in an innovative approach to awakening potential opportunities for interdisciplinarity, and enhance professional development for TEs during a period of substantial educational reform.

Keywords: Lesson study, teacher education, professional development

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Mathematics and language across borders: Exploring pedagogical actions on Irish-language use

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Abstract

Irish-medium education (IME) at primary level is a small but important sector of primary educational provision in both the Republic and the North of Ireland. While IME schools in both jurisdictions follow an immersion education approach aimed at achieving bilingualism in learners, the policy and curricular environment is otherwise quite different. This presentation reports on the Irish-language element of a broader study where two groups of primary teachers from north and south of the border engaged in an iterative cycle of lesson study intended to support professional learning and provide insight into teacher professional judgement in the teaching of high-quality fractions tasks in immersion contexts (Sarkar Arani et al., 2025).

Lesson study, a collaborative form of professional development which fosters the development of inquiring, agentic identities was used to build community and capacity. Through a collective inquiry into good teaching of high-quality mathematics tasks participating teachers were challenged to evaluate their pedagogical priorities across mathematics learning and language acquisition, within their differing policy contexts (Martinez et al., 2018). Planning meetings in the lesson study cycle were audio recorded, translated and transcribed. Lessons developed in these planning session were also recorded, transcribed and analysed. Analysis was conducted to address the following research questions:

1. Given a common task, how do teachers from different jurisdictions amend this task to cater to their pupil.
2. In immersion contexts, how do teachers address the dual challenge of language acquisition and development of mathematical conceptual understanding?

These questions are discussed with reference to both planning intentions, lesson actions and interview questions. The picture emerging indicates that teachers show awareness of language demands in their teaching and provide planned and responsive support in lessons. Responses to questions on the issue reveal teachers' views on perceived challenges for non-native speakers if Irish in learning mathematics.

Keywords: Mathematics teaching and learning, Immersion education, lesson study

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Supporting STEM Learning Through a Community partnership

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Abstract

In recent years, global interest in STEM education has grown substantially (English, 2016). Ireland's national *STEM Education Implementation plan to 2026* (DES 2017) has

created a roadmap and outlined the key stakeholders in the STEM education pipeline recognising the key role of parents and families as stakeholders in young children's STEM education. STEM education research has focused on developing learners' literacy (e.g. Falloon et al. 2020) and discussed the equitable access and opportunities in STEM education for all learners (e.g. Jackson et al. 2021). Many highlight failure to demonstrate three types of Epstein's (2002) Framework for *School, family, and community partnerships* specifically: parenting, decision-making, and community collaboration (Al Kafir, 2025). Given the key role of parents and communities in young children's learning and attitudes, this project addresses the need to explore and evaluate *how* we can best support parents, families and communities as key stakeholders in their children's STEM learning (Thomas et al. 2020).

This study aims to enhance science capital and parental engagement in primary STEM education, through accessible and participatory co-designed STEM workshops, informed by our stakeholders i.e. STEM education practitioners, children, families, and a range of family support services in a local community in the southwest region of Ireland.

The initiative includes parents as co-learners and role models to extend STEM learning beyond the classroom. The project uses practical, hands-on activities that combine high-tech and low-tech approaches to STEM education.

This model integrates participatory, co-designed workshops aimed to strengthen community engagement and impact, broaden participation in STEM education, and help adult learners view themselves as 'STEM Champions' in their local community.

This presentation will share the design and preliminary findings from this collaboration, discussing the opportunities, barriers and impact on parents, children and community supports in STEM learning through partnerships.

Keywords: STEM Outreach, Community Engagement, STEM Workshop

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A collection of first-hand experiences on gender EDI policies in HE mathematics

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Abstract

In the last past years, many higher education institutions in the world, and especially in Europe, have implemented policies toward gender equality, diversity and inclusivity. Even if studies have shown that these policies have had a positive impact, reports show that there are still very few women in leading positions in HE (Global Education Monitoring Report 2025: Gender Report: Women Lead for Learning, 2025) and this fact becomes more evident when we look at STEM-related fields, and mathematics among them, where the leaky pipeline phenomenon begins is strong. The goal of this research is to investigate the first-hand experience of mathematicians regarding gender equality, diversity and inclusivity in their departments, focusing on whether and how the EDI policies affect their work life. In this paper we present data collected through a survey asked to mathematicians, from bachelor students to lecturers, based in HE institutes around the world. It provides general feedback from mathematicians, and it is intended as a preliminary study to be developed into future projects. The questions asked focused on the psychological effects of gender quotas on all parties, the perception of gender EDI policies in HE mathematics, and the effects of a (non-)diversity of role models for future generations. The results highlight a gap between the implementation of the EDI policies and the true effectiveness of them. This research then provides a starting point for future targeted EDI policies in HE mathematics.

Keywords: EDI policies, Mathematics HE

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Global Education Monitoring Report 2025: Gender Report: Women Lead for Learning, 2025

Combating Gender Biases in the use of AI in Secondary Education through Feminist Education Innovations

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Abstract

As automated systems and AI become more integrated into everyday life, new techno-social realities emerge, bringing numerous ethical, social, and legal challenges (West et al., 2019). Combating gender discrimination from an intersectional perspective in the algorithmic context is one of the most important challenges of current digital societies (Castañeda-Jimenez et al., 2022). In this context, educators and students at different educational levels require educational strategies to address the complexities of AI's presence in the teaching-learning process.

The present educational intervention was developed within the framework of a pilot program promoted by the social and community theatre organization Plàudite Teatre in Barcelona (Spain), called #ACTFEM (Schaper et al., 2026). This program aims at researching social inclusion strategies for vulnerable young women and the prevention of early school leaving. Twelve students who belonged to a community at risk of social exclusion, aged 16 to 18, participated in a series of learning activities and discussion sessions related to the performing arts and AI use. One of these activities involved the co-creation of a play incorporating technology applied to the stage, whereas they also discussed ethical issues associated with the creation of AI images. Other educational activities were conducted to introduce and train a group of 36 secondary school teachers (mean of age = 45 years) from several disciplines in digital technologies within the context of educational AI use. Based on the co-creation sessions, a toolkit addressing secondary school teachers was designed with the purpose of gathering concrete strategies for engaging students through the promotion of critical and reflective learning processes about the use of AI in teaching, with a gender and intersectional approach. Feedback from teachers on the feasibility of implementing these activities in the classroom was also collected, as well as to co-design activities that enriched the content of the participants' teaching.

Keywords: Secondary Education, AI Tools, Gender biases

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Shaping STEM pathways through a female role model intervention

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Abstract

Drawing from expectancy-value theory (Eccles et al, 2020; Gonzalez et al., 2020), the goal of the present quasi-experimental study is to analyse the influence of a female role model intervention on girls' and boys' stereotypes and beliefs about math competencies, math utility value, and STEM aspirations. A total of 1400 secondary Spanish students (average age =15 years old) participated. In the first stage of the study all students were asked to answer a survey, whereas in the second part students were randomly assigned either to the experimental (they watched a video with three women working in STEM) or to the control group (they did not watch the video) before answering the survey. The video had an 18-minute duration, where three women working in STEM fields provided a short description of their career path, telling students what STEM careers encompass and advising them about how to pursue STEM professions. The results of the multi-group structural equation modelling analyses (controlling for school level) show that the role model sessions had a positive impact on students' self-concept of math ability, whereas it also enhanced the influence of STEM utility value on STEM-related career decisions. This effect was higher for women and students in the experimental group than those in the control group. In addition, all the E-V constructs mediated the relationship between gender stereotypes about math ability and STEM choices in both groups of males and females. The results suggest the importance of exposing secondary students from both genders to STEM female role models developing counter stereotypical roles in STEM fields.

Keywords: Role models, STEM, Motivation, Gender

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Building science capital among educationally disadvantaged youth: evidence from an observatory-based STEAM intervention

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Abstract

Participation in STEM remains socially patterned, with students from disadvantaged backgrounds persistently underrepresented. Variations in ‘science capital’, i.e., forms of economic, cultural and social capital that relate to science (Archer et al., 2015) have been proposed as a key factor underlying this phenomenon. The fusion of STEM and the arts (STEAM) has been recognised as a promising approach to broaden pathways to engagement and enhance equity in science learning (Rinne et al, 2011). This presentation reports on the findings from an independent evaluation of DIAS Dunsink Observatory’s Space Crafts programme, a series of onsite, three-day workshops for primary pupils attending designated disadvantaged (DEIS) schools. The workshops combined interactive science talks, demonstrations and arts-infused activities, providing a unique out-of-school learning experience designed to foster curiosity, confidence and identity in science. The evaluation addressed the overarching question of how participation the workshops influenced (i) pupils’ attitudes towards science and (ii) their scientific knowledge and skills. Conducted over 18 months, it employed a mixed methods design, drawing on pre-, post- and delayed (three-month) follow-up measures of pupils’ (n = 157, 53% male, aged 10-13) science-related attitudes and knowledge, alongside a series of post-workshop focus groups with pupils (n = 33) and interviews with teachers (n = 6). Linear mixed effects models indicated significant increases in pupils’ self-confidence in science, sustained at follow-up. Qualitative data revealed that the situated and creative nature of the learning, combined with a supportive, low-pressure environment had a positive impact on pupils’ curiosity about science, as well as their overall sense of what science involves and who can participate in it. These findings demonstrate that sustained gains in science confidence are achievable for young people with lower levels of science capital, highlighting how informal, arts-infused, place-based learning can contribute to addressing persistent inequities in science participation.

Keywords: science self-confidence, educational disadvantage, STEAM

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Enhancing STEM/STEAM Accessibility: Educator Awareness and Instructional Responses to Colour Vision Deficiency Through Experiential Learning

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Abstract

Colour vision deficiency (CVD) represents a persistent barrier to accessibility in STEM/STEAM education, particularly within digitally and visually intensive learning environments (Birch, 2012). As instructional tools increasingly rely on colour-coded digital interfaces and representations, students with CVD may experience frustration, reduced participation, and barriers to fully engaging with classroom learning and digital materials. Research has focused primarily on technological accommodation, and less attention has been given to how educators develop awareness of CVD. The literature shows that tools such as mobile applications, augmented reality (AR), colour-correcting technology, and non-colour-dependent instructional materials can decrease task difficulty, encourage independence, and improve learning outcomes (Chong et al., 2015; Harwahu et al., 2013; Huang et al., 2015; Melillo et al., 2017; Sharif et al., 2024).

This qualitative study examines how educators construct awareness of CVD and adapt instructional practices through classroom experiences. Grounded in Kolb's (1984) Experiential Learning Theory and Schön's (1983) reflective practitioner theory, the study explores how cycles of experience, reflection, and conceptualization shape educator decision-making in STEM/STEAM environments. Data will be analysed using thematic analysis informed by experiential learning and reflective practitioner frameworks to examine how awareness emerges over time and how educators adjust instruction in response to classroom experiences. The study explores how educators develop awareness of CVD through classroom interactions, student feedback, instructional challenges, and reflective practice. Data will be collected over a 12-week period beginning June 1, 2026, and will include educator narratives, surveys, instructional artefacts, and semi-structured interviews with STEM/STEAM educators. This development is associated with increased use of inclusive instructional strategies, including multisensory instruction, contrast-based design, and reduced reliance on colour-dependent communication. The study contributes to research on accessibility in STEM/STEAM education by highlighting how experiential learning processes influence inclusive instructional practice and educator decision-making.

Keywords: Colour vision deficiency (CVD), STEM/STEAM education, experiential learning theory

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Lab Technicians: glue, the buffer and the boundary spanner of the Science Education Team

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Abstract

Recent curriculum changes in Junior and Senior Cycle Science (NCCA, 2017, 2024) in Ireland mean that more subject matter integration and collaboration is required both at primary and secondary level. Science, as chemistry, biology and physics, is being absorbed into STEM education and must integrate with technology engineering and maths. This presents a new challenge to secondary teachers and university academics alike, who are trained as subject specialists. Teaching must adapt to those changes and as a result, subject specialists must cross over into unfamiliar disciplines.

Enter the science education laboratory technician. Primarily working behind the scenes, their cross-disciplinary subject matter and technical expertise, involvement in planning content, resourcing and delivery, and their interaction with students across programmes, positions the laboratory technician as the perfect boundary spanner across subjects for the multidisciplinary team of academics. In one university, an active community of practice (Wenger, 1998) within the science education team has developed organically, where a lab technician is employed specifically for science education, rather than general science. The lab technician, as knowledgeable-other, can guide collaborations, suggest and improve content, connect ideas and build resources to not only support but drive innovative pedagogy and practice from the core to the active layers.

This position paper will illustrate how academic staff in initial teacher science education can be supported to adapt to second level curriculum changes espousing an integrated STEM approach, by collaborating with the lab technician who brings a multidisciplinary approach to laboratory workshop design. It is essential that pre-service teachers (PSTs) leave university with the most up to date content and pedagogy for their subject. One example of the work of the community of practice where a biology specialist, a chemistry specialist and the lab technician cooperated to develop a practical activity that embeds analytical chemistry techniques into investigations in the new Leaving Certificate Biology curriculum. The chemistry behind biological processes is used to develop novel investigations to support PSTs content knowledge, skills and confidence. The paper will conclude by identifying potential future research in this novel area.

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(Re)Directing Attention, Embodying (In)Justice: Forum Theatre and Attentive Love in Science Teacher Education

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Abstract

Amidst accelerating climate change and expanding technoscientific capitalism, science education remains trapped in epistemological monocultures, privileging hierarchical knowledge systems, limiting our capacity to imagine alternative ways of being in the world (Author, 2025). This contribution explores how theatre-based pedagogies, inspired by Boal's forum theatre and Simone Weil's philosophy of attention, can create spaces for contesting hegemonic science narratives. Through collective scene-building and spectator interventions, educators physically embodied justice science issues (Morales-Doyle, 2024), i.e., environmental disasters in northern Chile and a museum's funding in the UK, making visible (and invisible) actors, temporal scales, and power relations typically absent from hegemonic science discussions. Preliminary analysis of participants' creations (interventions, reflective postcards) reveals how directing pedagogical attention—choosing what to look at and what to look away from—constitutes ethical, political, and pedagogical practices. By practising "suspending the I to see what truly exists", educators developed attentive ways of looking at the world that counter "affective numbness", and the myth of scientific neutrality. In doing so, participants discussed discomforts and potentials that embodied critical pedagogies open for just more-than-human futures. The intervention generated provocative questions for science teacher education such as: What aspects of science-society conflicts do we systematically not discuss? Where do our commitments lie, and in favour of whom, what, and against what do we teach science? What kind of solidarities and embodiments are we more um/comfortable with to embody?

Keywords: social justice science issues, embodied critical pedagogies, attentive love

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Gesture as a Pedagogical Resource in Undergraduate Mathematics

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Abstract

Mathematical thinking and understanding extend beyond verbal and written discourse: abstract mathematics is grounded through the *embodiment* of concepts (Lakoff & Núñez, 2000), and is frequently developed through *gesture*, defined as the spontaneous, idiosyncratic movements of the hands and arms that accompany speech (McNeill, 1992). Attending to students' (and teachers') gestures may therefore facilitate conceptual development in ways that many lectures in advanced mathematics do not (Lew et al., 2016).

Drawing on my teaching experiences and a larger study involving task-based interviews with undergraduate students with dyslexia, I present a series of pedagogical episodes. In these episodes, gesture emerges as a central semiotic resource for learning. It scaffolds mathematical information for processing, supports cognition in mentally demanding tasks, surfaces conceptual difficulties, and communicates nuance that the students' mathematical registers cannot yet express.

I examine how a lecturer can use gestural analysis to gain fresh insight into students' mathematical epistemologies, and respond to students' developing misconceptions by building on shared, inherently accessible, somatic resources. Building on this, a gesture-responsive pedagogical framework is proposed for noticing, interpreting, and supporting conceptual development in mathematics. This approach also enhances accessibility in undergraduate mathematics, particularly in conceptual activity where textual fluency is not the primary demand.

Keywords: undergraduate mathematics, embodiment, gesture analysis, pedagogical strategy.

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Developing Educator Noticing of Children's Mathematical Structural Awareness

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Abstract

The development of early mathematics is increasingly recognised as a foundational learning domain that strongly predicts later academic success (Clements & Sarama, 2014; Geary, 2017). This recognition has sparked a global shift toward 'mathematisation', defined as the process by which children formulate, employ, and interpret the world through mathematical concepts embedded in diverse, play-based contexts (OECD, 2021). Despite the organic emergence of mathematics in children's play, intentional pedagogy is required to bridge the gap between intuitive exploration and organised mathematical thinking (Ginsburg et al., 2008).

In Ireland, the central role of mathematics and numeracy is reflected in national policy frameworks. The Literacy, Numeracy and Digital Literacy (LNDL) Strategy 2024–2033 (Government of Ireland, 2024), the STEM Education Policy Statement 2017–2026 (DES, 2017), and Aistear, the national curriculum framework (NCCA, 2024), all frame numeracy as a fundamental life skill from birth.

Against this backdrop, we recently initiated a Professional Development (PD)-oriented intervention study in a Dublin pre-school setting that aims to increase awareness of tasks and resources that can be used within play-based pedagogies to enhance children's structural awareness of early number. Structural awareness is defined as the attention to number relationships in ordinal, cardinal and part-whole senses.

The development of educators' mathematical knowledge and pedagogical practice is central to the implementation of this research. To support this, monthly whole-setting training and reflective sessions are conducted, and supplemented with classroom visits. Monthly meetings provide an opportunity to build on educators' knowledge and plan for the coming month based on educators' reports of children's progress and play interests. Classroom visits provide an opportunity to observe and discuss the implementation of plans and to examine individual children's development and needs.

In our presentation, we share current insights into the development of educator noticing in children's mathematical thinking and development.

Keywords: Educator noticing, Children's mathematical development, Professional development

Mapping pre-school early number learning progressions

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Abstract

A stated aim of the AISTEAR Early Childhood Curriculum Framework (NCCA, 2024) is for young children to: 'broaden their understanding of the world by making sense of their world through emergent literacy and numeracy experiences' (p.27). Prior research notes that for pre-school educators to support emergent numeracy experiences, they need strong mathematical content knowledge and competence in communicating this knowledge appropriately alongside awareness of children's mathematical development (Gasteiger & Benz, 2018). However, O'Neill, Gillic and Kingston (2022) noted that mathematics modules were not mandatory in Irish early childhood initial teacher education programmes. Consequently, there are gaps in educator awareness of learning progressions, and need for resources and professional development (PD) to build this awareness.

We recently began a PD-oriented intervention study located in a Dublin pre-school setting that seeks to build awareness of tasks and resources that can be used within play-based pedagogies to build children's structural awareness of early number. By structural awareness, we mean attention to number relationships in ordinal, cardinal and part-whole senses. Structural awareness can be contrasted with approaches based on counting in ones, because – in the latter approaches – no use is made of number relationships to support more efficient counting. For example, some young children, when shown one hand with all fingers open and a second hand with two fingers open, can say: 'Five. Six, seven. Seven fingers.' This approach, in contrast to counting all fingers from 1, depends on knowledge of the ordinal number sequence where 6 and 7 follow 5.

In our presentation, we share our turning of baseline individual interview data from n=18 cross-attainment 3-/ 4-year olds through literature-based structural relation content analysis into pragmatic progression 'maps' that educators can use to note changes in children's working.

Keywords: ECE, early number learning, learning progressions

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Youth facilitators' mathematical knowledge

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Abstract

In South Africa, recent figures from the Quarterly Labour Force Survey (Stats SA, 2025) show that close to half (46.1%) of youth aged 15-34 are unemployed. In this context, some NGOs in the education sector have recruited youth facilitators to support primary mathematics teaching and learning. Our study relates to one NGO that has recruited youth facilitators to lead after school maths clubs for grade 3 and 4 pupils with extensive gaps in understandings of early grade mathematics. Youth facilitator recruitment involved advertising to unemployed youth living near the schools. Selection was based on a basic numeracy test and an interview.

A key focus for the NGO, given the limited evidence base on the nature of youth facilitators' mathematical knowledge, is to understand the mathematical knowledge base of this group. In this presentation, we share baseline analyses on the mathematical/didactical knowledge of a cohort of youth facilitators drawn from across three provinces. The data was collected early in 2026 preceding the youth facilitators' participation in a hybrid WhatsApp/online platform-based professional development programme that seeks to equip Maths Clubs leaders with stronger foundations in the mathematical and didactical knowledge needed to teach productively. This data was drawn from a written pre-test administered to the youth facilitator cohort (n=240), and from task-based interviews conducted with a sub-sample of n=22 youth facilitators.

Our findings detail the mathematical and didactical knowledge base among youth facilitators and make comparisons with the findings seen from similar data collected previously by the NGO from primary teachers leading Maths Clubs in their programme (Bowie & Venkat, forthcoming). We discuss implications from our findings for considering extensions to programmes working to improve primary mathematics learning using youth facilitators.

Keywords: youth facilitators, early grade mathematics, South Africa, mathematical knowledge for teaching, Maths Clubs

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‘STEAM from the Start’: A Human-centred, Community Responsive Framework for Sustainable STEAM Integration in Early Childhood Education

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Abstract

While STEAM's benefits are well established, educators often lack the confidence and competence to implement STEAM meaningfully post-training (DeJarnette 2018; Jamil et al. 2018). This research engaged constructivist grounded theory as existing frameworks such as TPACK (Mishra 2019) were not designed for transdisciplinary STEAM and the SCALE model (Quigley et al. 2017) was not specifically designed for ECEC pedagogy.

Across two phases, six themes influencing current STEAM practice were identified and grouped under two core factors: willingness (educators' beliefs about STEAM's importance) and ability (practical knowledge, skills, and structural supports). These insights informed the novel 'STEAM from the Start' conceptual framework (Walshe et al. 2025), which shaped a STEAM CPD workshop designed to strengthen educators' STEAM capacity aligning with STEAM education policy and guidelines.

Data was gathered using a mixed method approach engaging surveys and focus groups and analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke 2019). Data gathered from phase one surveys ($n=245$) and focus group participants ($n=6$) informed the development of the conceptual framework and CPD intervention delivered to ECEC educators ($n=153$) nationally. Phase two data was gathered at three intervals to determine short-, medium- and long-term impact.

Short-term: surveys ($n=142$) undertaken on day of CPD intervention indicated increased confidence, confidence and understanding and reduced barriers.

Medium-term: focus group data engaged participants ($n=7$) gathered 2-months post CPD showed intentional, collaborative, curriculum aligned STEAM integration.

Long-term: surveys ($n=7$) undertaken 9-months post-training indicated sustained engagement supported by post-workshop resources and self-directed CPD.

This research demonstrates the necessity of addressing both willingness and ability to develop effective STEAM CPD interventions which translate into long-term, meaningful change in pedagogical practice and highlights the value of grounding CPD in educators lived experience. Recommendations include exploring scalability, leveraging non-screen, unplugged technologies, and adapting the framework to emerging pedagogies such as AI, AR.

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Curricular Reform: Considering the role of the growth mindset of Curriculum leaders, through the lens of the Primary Mathematics curriculum (PMC) 2023.

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Abstract

This doctoral research critically examines how curriculum leaders who model and enact a growth mindset can support the meaningful embedding of the Primary Mathematics Curriculum (PMC, 2023) in Irish primary schools. Moving beyond compliance-driven reform, the study conceptualises curriculum change as a complex, socially mediated process shaped by leadership beliefs, professional dispositions, and relational practices. It explores how leaders’ epistemological orientations influence teachers’ engagement with reform and contributes to the development of pupils’ mathematical identity and productive disposition.

The research is grounded in Dweck's theory of growth mindset and Kilpatrick et al.'s construct of productive disposition, situated within a broader socio cognitive and organisational framework. Bandura's theory of self-efficacy informs analysis of teacher agency and confidence, while Schein's work on organisational culture and Hargreaves and Fullan's concept of professional capital frame the cultural conditions necessary for sustained change. Drawing on Coburn's notion of reform depth and Ball et al.'s policy enactment framework, growth mindset is conceptualised not as an individual strategy, but as embedded within a wider ecology of leadership, collaboration, and systemic alignment.

Within the PMC context, this ecology is critical, as the curriculum foregrounds learner agency, problem-solving, and the development of positive and productive dispositions. However, tensions may arise where performative assessment cultures, time constraints, or entrenched beliefs persist, risking superficial enactment. From a policy enactment perspective, teachers actively interpret reform within local constraints, and misalignment can result in shallow implementation.

Methodologically, the study adopts a qualitative longitudinal design, involving three semi-structured interviews over nine months with ten curriculum leaders (Principals, Deputies, AP1 and AP2 as well as teachers who lead maths) across diverse school contexts. Thematic analysis is used to examine leadership practices and cultural dynamics shaping reform enactment. The study aims to generate insights into how leadership mindset mediates sustainable curriculum change and supports the realisation of the PMC's vision.

Keywords: Leading, Change, Mindset

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Four Seasons One World: A Project from the Towards Inclusion Pilot Program

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Abstract

This paper discusses an interschool collaborative project between a special school and a mainstream primary school funded by the "Towards Inclusion" pilot program. This interschool collaboration initiative involved 38 geographically paired schools across Ireland. Program activities are grounded in sound pedagogy, prioritizing clear learning outcomes, fostering student motivation, and catering to the diverse learning needs of all participants, particularly those with Special Educational Needs (SEN).

The program's expected outcomes include enhanced educational outcomes for students with SEN, substantial professional development, supporting diverse needs, strengthened collaboration, sharing best practices. A core strategy involved reciprocal arrangements for teachers to observe and participate in lessons within their paired school, deepening their understanding of various learning needs and how they are effectively addressed in different contexts. Schools had autonomy in developing their own specific project with ongoing support from the NCSE.

The science of climatology was the inspiration for thAs well as providing insights on interschool collaboration, the project is also an example of accessibility is project running over 12 weeks culminating in a show celebrating the four seasons. This project provides an example of accessibility and context in science education (Hüfner et al, 2025).

Findings include the opportunity for sharing expertise was transformative, challenging the isolating nature of classroom teaching and allowing educators to participate in authentic inclusive practices in action and students also contributing. This school-based professional development was reported as highly relational and authentic. Furthermore, teacher responses noted high levels of student engagement and enthusiasm, with children making new friends and exploring new settings. Building strong, trusting relationships between schools that had no prior connection was also noted as challenging, yet ultimately rewarding. The outcomes were evaluated through reflective responses from teachers and students (Essex J, 2020).

The Towards Inclusion pilot represents a promising model for building capacity in inclusive education through authentic, reciprocal professional development and

collaborative school networks, with lessons learned poised to inform future national policy on inclusion and school partnerships.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Science, Curriculum

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